

A Review and Assessment of the Climate Change Anxiety in Yangon

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1. INTRODUCTION

Climate change is a pressing global issue that presents substantial threats to the environment, human health, and socio-economic development. It refers to the long-term alterations in the Earth's climate system, encompassing changes in global temperature, precipitation patterns, and sea levels, primarily driven by human activities such as the combustion of fossil fuels, deforestation, and agricultural practices. Recognizing the gravity of this challenge, the United Nations Climate Summit in New York identified climate change as the defining problem of the 21st century, while the Australian Medical Association declared it a health emergency in 2019. These declarations serve as poignant reminders that climate change is an ongoing phenomenon, exhibiting no signs of abatement, and yielding increasingly dire consequences. In substantiating the presence of climate change and its effects, empirical evidence provided by NASA reveals that the average surface temperature of the Earth in 2022 is tied with that of 2015 as the fifth warmest on record (NASA, 2023). Moreover, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) underscores in its Sixth Assessment Report that climate change has induced species losses, augmented disease prevalence, and triggered mass mortality events among both plant and animal populations. Consequently, these climatic shifts have precipitated the occurrence of climate-driven extinctions, reconfiguration of ecosystems, amplified wildfire-ravaged areas, and diminished crucial ecosystem functions (IPCC, 2022). Thus, the impact of climate change is felt globally, albeit with certain regions, such as Southeast Asia, exhibiting heightened vulnerability to its consequences.

In order to understand climate change anxiety better and to avoid further confusion within the paper, first, the definitions of eco-anxiety and climate change anxiety need to be distinguished and clarified. Due to the fact that it is a relatively new field of research not only to the international community but also to the country of Myanmar, definitions of both eco-anxiety and climate change anxiety as well as the differences between them are still being studied and examined although the terms have gradually gained traction in the media and among researchers over the years (Coffey et al., 2021). Throughout most research, it was also

found that the words eco-anxiety and climate change anxiety are used, to some extent, interchangeably. Nevertheless, through analysis and research of many kinds of literature, the authors have identified some terminological differences between them. In 2017, the American Psychological Association (APA) and EcoAmerica introduced the concept of eco-anxiety, which they defined as a chronic fear of environmental doom. However, alternative perspectives on eco-anxiety have also been proposed. According to Usher et al. (2019), eco-anxiety can be understood as a form of psychological distress or unease stemming from concerns about the detrimental consequences of environmental degradation, including climate change, pollution, and sea-level rise. Several research papers have employed different terms to describe the eco-anxiety induced by environmental issues. For instance, Mallett (2012), in the book "Eco-Guilt motivates Eco-Friendly Behaviour," introduced the term eco-guilt, which refers to feelings of guilt arising when individuals reflect on instances where they have not met personal or societal standards of environmental behaviour. While some argue that eco-guilt may diminish motivation to engage in pro-environmental actions, Mallett opposes this view, suggesting that eco-guilt can actually promote greater pro-environmental behaviour. Another term associated with eco-anxiety is eco-grief, defined by Comtesse et al. (2021) as the experience of grief in response to past or anticipated ecological losses. Additionally, eco-angst, as described by Goleman (2019), denotes a sense of hopelessness or despair arising from the precarious state of the planet's environmental health.

On the one hand, Collier (2022) of Harvard Medical School has provided a definition of climate change anxiety as the emotional stress and worry resulting from perceived or actual threats associated with climate change. Similarly, the Handbook of Climate Psychology published by the Climate Psychology Alliance (CPA) (2020) defines climate change anxiety as an intensified experience of emotional, mental, or physical suffering in response to significant changes in the climate system. It has been suggested that climate change anxiety is a subset of eco-anxiety, both of which contribute to the impact of planetary conditions on our mental health. Previous research has examined the connection between the fear of nuclear war and this phenomenon (Pihkala, 2019). In these contexts, it is important to note that neither eco-anxiety nor climate change anxiety can be classified as a disease or psychological disorder. Instead, they are considered symptoms arising from feelings of helplessness and despair when confronted with the daunting challenges posed by environmental problems and, to some extent, climate change. Nevertheless, in severe cases, eco-anxiety or climate change anxiety may contribute to mental health issues such as Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD), sleep deprivation, depression, substance abuse, and physical ailments (National Institute of Mental

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Health and Neuro Science, India, 2016). By analysing these two definitions of eco-anxiety and climate change anxiety, we observe that while climate change anxiety specifically refers to anxiety or mental distress caused by climate change and its consequences, eco-anxiety encompasses a broader phenomenon that includes climate change anxiety. It encompasses psychological distress resulting from various environmental issues, including pollution, wildfires, and global warming, among others.

Figure 1.1 Concerns regarding Climate Change (Thompson, 2021)

Mr. Tosin Thompson from Nature Journal conducted a survey of 10,000 young people aged 16 to 25 from 10 countries has revealed that climate change is causing distress, anger, and other negative emotions among children and youth worldwide. Referred to as 'eco-anxiety,' these emotions have a detrimental impact on their daily lives, partly due to the perception that governments are not doing enough to prevent a climate catastrophe. The study, the largest of its kind, found that nearly 60% of respondents expressed significant worry about climate change, with common associated emotions including sadness, fear, anxiety, anger, and powerlessness. Furthermore, 45% of participants reported that their feelings about climate change influenced their daily lives. This research highlights the need to address climate change as a dimension of youth mental health concerns and emphasizes the urgency for stronger government actions in mitigating climate change effects Figure 1.1 of the study presents the percentage of respondents who expressed concern regarding climate change. The findings indicate the level of worry among the surveyed young individuals, with the chart providing a visual representation of the distribution. Conversely, Figure 1.2 provides insights into the emotions experienced by the participants in relation to climate change. The graph displays the

frequencies of specific negative emotions associated with climate change, offering a comprehensive understanding of the psychological impact experienced by the respondents. These visual representations contribute to the overall analysis of the study, providing valuable information on the extent of concern and emotional responses related to climate change among young individuals.

Figure 1.2 Respondents emotions regarding Climate Change (Thompson, 2021)

Myanmar, located in Southeast Asia, is a country highly vulnerable to the negative consequences of climate change due to its geographical location, low-lying delta regions, and dependence on natural resources. Extensive literature and research have highlighted the specific challenges faced by Myanmar in relation to climate change. Studies have shown that Myanmar is experiencing observable impacts of climate change. Rising temperatures have been documented, leading to heatwaves and increased heat-related illnesses. Erratic precipitation patterns, including irregular rainfall and prolonged droughts, have become more frequent, affecting agricultural productivity and exacerbating water scarcity issues (UN-Habitat, 2019). The country has also witnessed an increase in extreme weather events, such as cyclones and storms, leading to widespread damage, loss of lives, and displacement (Ghimire et al., 2022). These environmental changes have had significant consequences for the people of Myanmar. Environmental degradation, including deforestation and soil erosion, has impacted the livelihoods of rural communities heavily reliant on agriculture and forestry. Losses in crop yields, reduced fish stocks, and decreased availability of clean water have led

to food insecurity and economic instability. Furthermore, the displacement of communities due to climate-induced disasters has resulted in the loss of homes, assets, and social support systems, amplifying the vulnerabilities and stress experienced by affected populations. Within this context, the emergence of climate change anxiety as a distinct form of psychological distress in Myanmar's population, including those residing in urban centres like Yangon, has been recognized. Although there is limited research specifically focusing on climate change anxiety in Myanmar, the broader literature on the psychological impacts of climate change provides insights into this phenomenon. The aforementioned definition of climate change anxiety as emotional stress and worry caused by perceived or real threats of climate change (Collier, 2022) aligns with the experiences of individuals in Myanmar. Moreover, the notion of climate change anxiety as a subset of eco-anxiety has been explored in the literature. Eco-anxiety encompasses a broader range of psychological distress resulting from various environmental issues, and climate change anxiety can be seen as a specific manifestation within this broader framework (Clayton, 2020 & Climate Psychology Alliance, 2020). While eco-anxiety has been associated with adverse mental health outcomes, including anxiety disorders, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder, the specific impacts of climate change anxiety on mental well-being in the context of Myanmar require further investigation (National Institute of Mental Health and Neuro Science, India, 2016 & Schwartz, 2022).

The main mission of this research paper is to examine and assess the occurrence of climate change anxiety in Yangon City, Myanmar, a city that confronts substantial environmental adversities as the commercial centre of the country. Yangon, with a population exceeding seven million, stands as Myanmar's largest city and is positioned along the Yangon River delta, rendering it prone to rising sea levels and flooding. The swift urbanisation of Yangon has resulted in significant environmental deterioration, encompassing issues such as air and water pollution as well as deforestation, amplifying its susceptibility to the impacts of climate change. This study seeks to accomplish several objectives: (1) conduct a comprehensive review of existing literature on climate change anxiety to enhance understanding of the relationship between climate change and anxiety; (2) Selecting the most influencing key factors on climate change anxiety in Myanmar (3) examine the current situation of individuals residing in the study area; and (4) propose effective and sustainable solutions to address the identified issue. Employing a qualitative research approach, the study draws upon secondary data from multiple literature reviews and expert interviews, as well as primary data derived from online surveys. Although the study's findings may possess certain limitations, they will make a substantial contribution to the existing body of literature on climate change

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anxiety in Myanmar, offering valuable insights into the experiences of individuals in developing nations confronted by this phenomenon. Furthermore, the study will provide policymakers and organisations with recommendations on how to address climate change anxiety within vulnerable communities, particularly in Yangon.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Study on relation between Climate Change and Anxiety

Climate change is not solely an environmental concern; it also has psychological implications. The rise in climate change anxiety, characterised by feelings of concern, hopelessness, and remorse, can be attributed to the uncertainty surrounding climate change and the global response. Young individuals, who are projected to bear the brunt of climate change impacts throughout their lifetimes, are particularly vulnerable to experiencing this emotional distress. Climate change anxiety is associated with various mental health issues, including panic attacks, appetite loss, and insomnia. Moreover, its prevalence has been linked to socioeconomic factors such as fluctuations in birth rates. Extensive research, encompassing investigations into the psychometric properties of climate change anxiety assessment tools, underscores the significance of this issue, necessitating careful consideration. While climate change anxiety may foster pro-environmental behaviour, it can also contribute to severe psychological disorders such as anxiety disorders, panic attacks, and insomnia. Consequently, the provision of competent and effective mental health care is crucial for mitigating the adverse impacts of climate change distress, particularly among vulnerable populations such as young individuals.

Based on an extensive literature review, the relationship between climate change anxiety and behaviour is intricate and inadequately comprehended. There is a hypothesis suggesting that climate change anxiety may act as a driving force, motivating individuals to adopt pro-environmental behaviour. However, it is also postulated that climate change anxiety can lead to a state of "eco-paralysis," where individuals are immobilised and unable to take effective action. The comprehension of how climate anxiety influences behaviour and its implications for addressing climate change constitutes a critical research area that necessitates further investigation. Although some studies have indicated a positive association between climate change anxiety and pro-environmental behaviour, the underlying mechanisms and factors contributing to this relationship remain poorly understood. Additionally, conflicting findings and inconclusive evidence necessitate a more nuanced and comprehensive understanding of the dynamics between climate anxiety and behaviour. Researchers need to explore the potential mediating and moderating variables that may influence the relationship between climate change anxiety and pro-environmental behaviour. Furthermore, the concept of "eco-paralysis" underscores the potential detrimental impact of climate change anxiety on individuals' ability to take effective action. It is essential to investigate the psychological processes and underlying causes that contribute to this state of paralysis, including factors such

as perceived self-efficacy, coping mechanisms, and social norms. By identifying the barriers and facilitators associated with climate change anxiety and behaviour, researchers can develop targeted interventions and strategies to promote adaptive responses to climate change.

Climate change anxiety has gained increasing attention as a field of study examining the relationship between geophysical climate change and its impact on mental health. Empirical research has provided support for the existence of climate anxiety, demonstrating that the perception of environmental change can have detrimental effects on mental well-being, including heightened distress and anxiety. In popular discourse, climate change anxiety has been referred to by various terms such as "eco-anxiety" or "climate grief," reflecting the emotional and psychological toll experienced by individuals in response to the challenges posed by climate change. These terms capture the deep concern, fear, and sadness that individuals may experience as they witness the impacts of climate change on ecosystems, communities, and future prospects. Moreover, it is worth noting that climate change anxiety is not uniformly distributed among populations. Research suggests that individuals who possess a strong connection to and concern for environmental issues, as well as those who have personally witnessed or experienced the effects of climate change, may be more prone to climate change anxiety. This highlights the subjective and contextual nature of climate anxiety and its relationship to personal experiences and values. It is important to continue studying and understanding climate change anxiety, as it contributes to our comprehension of the intersection between environmental challenges and mental health. By identifying the underlying mechanisms, individual and societal responses, and potential coping strategies associated with climate change anxiety, researchers can inform the development of effective interventions and support systems to address the psychological impacts of climate change on individuals and communities.

2.2 Reviewing Influencing Factors

The identification and understanding of influencing factors on climate change anxiety are crucial for studying and assessing this phenomenon comprehensively. These factors provide insights into the complexity of climate change anxiety and help researchers and practitioners develop a more nuanced understanding of its causes, consequences, and potential interventions. Demographic factors, such as age and gender, can shed light on how different segments of the population may be more vulnerable or resilient to climate change anxiety. For example, younger individuals who anticipate longer exposure to the impacts of climate change may experience higher levels of anxiety. Socio-economic factors, including occupation and

income, can reveal disparities in resources and adaptive capacities, which can influence the degree of climate change anxiety experienced by individuals and communities. Environmental factors, such as exposure to natural disasters or environmental degradation, are important considerations as they directly affect the lived experiences and perceptions of individuals. Understanding the relationship between climate change events and subsequent anxiety responses can inform disaster preparedness efforts and resilience-building strategies. Health factors, including pre-existing conditions, can interact with climate change anxiety, amplifying its impact on individuals' mental health and well-being. Certain health conditions may render individuals more vulnerable to the psychological effects of climate change and require tailored support and care.

Additionally, general factors such as environmental consciousness and media use play a role in shaping individuals' awareness, attitudes, and responses to climate change anxiety. Environmental consciousness can influence the level of concern individuals feel towards environmental issues, while media use can both amplify or mitigate anxiety levels by shaping public narratives and information dissemination. By considering these influencing factors, researchers and practitioners can design more effective assessments, interventions, and policies to address climate change anxiety. This comprehensive understanding allows for targeted support systems, public awareness campaigns, and mental health interventions that consider the specific needs and vulnerabilities associated with different demographic, socio-economic, environmental, health, and general factors. Ultimately, these efforts aim to mitigate the detrimental effects of climate change anxiety and promote resilience in individuals and communities.

2.2.1 Demographic Factors

Climate change anxiety is a multifaceted issue influenced by various demographic factors, including gender, age, and race. Research has increasingly explored the association between climate change and psychological distress, encompassing stress, anxiety, anger, and even suicidal ideation among men, as well as the impact of intimate partner violence on women (Closson et al., 2021). However, it is important to acknowledge that climate change anxiety may not affect all individuals equally. Specifically, women may be more vulnerable to the psychological effects of climate change due to perceived power differentials in many societies (World Health Organization, 2014). Gender disparities are evident in terms of women's limited participation in decision-making processes and their constrained access to and control over agricultural resources and services necessary for climate change adaptation (Aguilar et al.,

2008). A recent survey conducted in 2021 found that a higher proportion of women reported experiencing climate change anxiety compared to men, potentially influenced by societal expectations regarding male emotional expression (Closson et al., 2021). Given that women exhibit greater pro-environmental attitudes compared to men, this gender difference in climate change apprehension may hinder environmental action among women, thereby impeding collective efforts to address climate change. Therefore, it is imperative to ensure equal consideration and inclusion of women in discussions and interventions related to climate change anxiety.

Research indicates that younger generations tend to exhibit higher levels of climate change anxiety compared to older generations. This generational difference can be attributed to several factors. Emerging evidence suggests that young people are particularly susceptible to the indirect impacts of climate change, including climate change anxiety, which can have significant implications for their psychosocial health and well-being. In fact, climate change anxiety has been found to exacerbate pre-existing mental health issues in some children (Hickerman et al., 2021). One key contributing factor to the heightened climate change anxiety among young people is their perception of an uncertain future and a sense of doom for humanity. Many young individuals grappling with climate change anxiety harbor concerns that their prospects are compromised and that the planet's future is bleak. Notably, millennials and Generation Z cohorts have displayed higher levels of environmental consciousness and activism compared to Baby Boomers and Generation X. The experience of anxiety associated with climate change can serve as a motivational force for young people, driving them towards pro-environmental actions. Given the active engagement of young individuals in environmental causes, it becomes imperative to provide them with ample opportunities to express their concerns and take on leadership roles. By empowering young people and fostering their participation, their unique perspectives and contributions can be harnessed to address the challenges posed by climate change effectively.

The influence of race or ethnicity on climate change anxiety is a significant aspect to consider, particularly given the disproportionate impact of climate change on disadvantaged communities and marginalised groups, such as people of colour, who often face socioeconomic inequities. Research conducted by Ballew et al. (2020) highlights that individuals belonging to ethnic minority groups in the United States exhibit higher levels of anxiety related to climate change. Specifically, the study found that 70% of Hispanic/Latino individuals and 57% of African-American individuals expressed concerns about climate change. Similar patterns have been observed in other regions worldwide. Notably, nations that are particularly vulnerable to

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the consequences of climate change, such as those in the Middle East and Southeast Asia, often exhibit a heightened level of concern and anxiety regarding this issue compared to their counterparts in Western countries. This discrepancy can be attributed to the greater exposure of these regions to environmental hazards and extreme weather events, which disproportionately affect individuals of color, even within developed nations. Understanding the relationship between race or ethnicity and climate change anxiety is essential for comprehending the multifaceted nature of this phenomenon. It highlights the intersectionality of climate change impacts, socioeconomic disparities, and environmental justice concerns. Acknowledging and addressing the unique experiences and vulnerabilities of marginalised communities is crucial for developing inclusive and effective strategies to mitigate climate change anxiety and promote equitable adaptation and resilience.

2.2.2 Socio-economics Factors

Socio-economic factors, including occupation, income, and economic and political stability (EPS), can play a significant role in shaping an individual's perception of climate change and their experience of climate change anxiety. While there is a lack of formal documentation specifically addressing the occupational implications of climate change anxiety, it can be postulated that there is a correlation between one's profession and their vulnerability to climate change anxiety. This suggests that an individual's occupation may influence how they perceive climate change and the likelihood of experiencing anxiety related to it. Certain occupations, particularly those that involve extensive exposure to natural elements, such as farming, construction, and transportation, are more susceptible to the impacts of climate change. Consequently, individuals in these professions face an elevated risk of experiencing climate-induced mental health hazards, particularly in relation to phenomena like droughts, heatwaves, and floods. Prolonged droughts, for example, have been associated with adverse consequences such as degraded economic conditions, reduced social functioning, and psychological detachment from the negative effects of climatic conditions. It is important to recognize the link between socio-economic factors, occupation, and climate change anxiety as it sheds light on the differential vulnerabilities and challenges faced by individuals in various professions. By understanding the specific occupational contexts and associated risks, interventions and support systems can be developed to address the mental health impacts of climate change on individuals in high-risk occupations. Additionally, policies and measures aimed at promoting economic stability and social well-being can contribute to reducing the psychological toll of climate change among affected populations.

There is a possibility that individuals belonging to lower income groups, who are generally more vulnerable to environmental hazards, may experience greater levels of climate anxiety. However, a study investigating this relationship found no significant association though it is important to consider the fundamental human necessities and aspirations, such as food, clothing, and housing, which have also been found to be positively correlated with climate anxiety, as per another study conducted by Wullenkord et al. in 2021. It can be inferred that individuals who possess high-middle or high incomes for either themselves or their families exhibit a reduced level of worry or distress towards climate change, as their fundamental necessities have been fulfilled. A positive correlation was observed between increased income and a greater willingness to adjust to climate change (Schwirplies, 2017). The anxiety surrounding climate change can be influenced by the political and economic stability of a region. Instances of economic and political instability can lead to a range of adverse outcomes, including food shortages, economic recessions, and unemployment, which can significantly increase the risk of mental health issues, including suicide and other behavioural disorders. This relationship between climate change anxiety, political instability, and economic conditions can be observed in the context of Myanmar (Burma).

For example, in Myanmar, the country has experienced a severe economic and political collapse as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 and a political situation in 2021. These events have had a profound impact on the well-being of the population, leading to an increase in anxiety disorders and suicide rates (Frontier Myanmar, 2022). This demonstrates how economic and political instability can exacerbate mental health challenges in the face of climate change. Moreover, climate change itself can contribute to economic and political problems, as the occurrence of severe weather events imposes significant financial burdens on businesses and governments worldwide, amounting to billions of dollars in losses each year. These financial concerns further raise apprehensions regarding the consequences of climate change (Fountoulakis et al., 2016). The interplay between economic and climatic factors has been found to be associated with variations in suicide rates, with different rates observed among males and females in different regions (Fountoulakis et al., 2016). By understanding the intricate connections between climate change anxiety, political stability, and economic conditions, policymakers and researchers can recognize the multifaceted impacts of climate change on mental health. This knowledge underscores the importance of considering the broader socio-political and economic context when addressing climate change anxiety and developing appropriate interventions. Efforts aimed at promoting political stability, economic

resilience, and mental health support can contribute to mitigating the adverse psychological effects of climate change and building resilience in affected communities.

2.2.3 Environmental Factors

The significance of environmental factors, such as natural disasters, has increased in relation to climate change concerns. This is due to their ability to cause congenital abnormalities and even mental health disorders. A significant proportion of individuals exposed to climate- or weather-related natural disasters, such as heatwaves, cyclones, and deforestation, experience adverse psychological effects, including stress and severe mental health implications. There seems to be a link between heat waves and both physical and mental health. According to Paolo et al. (2020), the Climate and Health Profile Report, jointly published by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), has acknowledged the direct and indirect health consequences of extreme heat. The adverse physical health effects of heat waves include heat exhaustion, acute dehydration, and in extreme cases, mortality. These effects are most pronounced among vulnerable populations in developing nations whose livelihoods rely heavily on outdoor employment. In addition, heat surges have been associated with deleterious psychological effects, which can contribute to climate change-related anxiety. Indirectly, heat surges can also cause drought, diminished food security, and wildfires, all of which can amplify climate change anxiety. According to Clayton et al. (2017), the risk of death due to heat waves is three times higher for those with mental illness compared to those without such conditions. Women, young adults, and those with limited financial resources are more susceptible to anxiety and mood disorders in the aftermath of disasters, according to the World Health Organization (2014). It has been observed that heat waves may lead to an increase in individual aggression and violence. According to Anderson's (2001) research, there is a higher incidence of heat-related violence during sweltering summers and in years with elevated temperatures. Moreover, although there is no formal evidence to support this observation, it appears that nations in milder tropical regions have lower levels of development than those in harsher climates. Consequently, it is vital to implement preventative measures to mitigate the negative effects of extreme temperatures on public health.

Severe storms, such as cyclones, hurricanes, and typhoons, can have profound and lasting impacts on both physical and mental health. Extensive research has demonstrated that the aftermath of these storms, characterised by the loss of loved ones, destruction of property, and significant economic damage, can contribute to various mental health challenges, including

anxiety, depression, and Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) that may persist for years (Lee Health, 2022). One striking example of the detrimental effects of a cyclone is the 2008 Nargis Cyclone in Myanmar. The Nargis Cyclone, classified as a category four storm, struck Myanmar's Ayeyarwady Delta in 2008, resulting in a devastating toll. According to reports, an estimated 133,000 people were reported dead or missing in the aftermath of the cyclone, while an additional 2.4 million individuals were plunged into poverty due to a delayed and disjointed government response (United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs, 2008). Survivors of the cyclone were left traumatized, with vivid memories of the catastrophic events, particularly the sight of their loved ones being carried away or lost in the 35-kilometre inland tidal surge. The United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (2008) documented the psychological impact on survivors, including children, who exhibited symptoms such as anxiety, sleep disturbances, despair, withdrawal, and even suicidal thoughts. These findings highlight the urgent need for not only physical assistance but also emotional and psychological support for individuals who have endured the traumatic experiences caused by hurricanes. Recognizing the mental health consequences of severe storms is crucial in providing comprehensive aid to affected communities. Alongside efforts to provide physical assistance and rebuild infrastructure, it is essential to prioritise emotional support and mental health services for survivors. Providing a safe and supportive environment, addressing trauma-related symptoms, and promoting resilience can help individuals in their recovery process.

The ever-increasing intensity of climate change brought on by global warming has resulted in numerous casualties and, consequently, climate change anxiety. It is widely acknowledged that deforestation causes global warming or climate change. National Geographic Society defines deforestation as the intentional clearance of forested lands for grazing, agriculture, timber, construction, and transportation (National Geographic Society, 2022). Deforestation has significantly altered global landscapes. 80 percent of Western Europe was forested approximately 2,000 years ago, but only 34 percent is today (National Geographic Society, 2022). Moreover, in the case of the Amazon Rainforest in South America, according to a Time magazine article, with 20 percent of the forest gone, scientists estimate that, at the present rate of deforestation, 27 percent of the Amazon will be gone forever by 2030 (Sandy, 2022). Similarly, routine deforestation occurs in the nation of Myanmar. Myanmar is reportedly the most vegetated country in Southeast Asia, but also the most deforested, due to excessive harvesting for fuel, plantations, and money, as well as illicit logging (Myanmar Information Management Unit, 2022). In 1948, 77% of the country was covered by forests; however, between 1992 and 2015, the forest cover decreased significantly from 60% to 44%, and

between 2000 and 2020, the deforestation rate increased from 1% to 2.5%, making Myanmar one of the top ten countries worldwide for deforestation (Myanmar Information Management Unit, 2022). People who have been directly and profoundly affected by deforestation, particularly indigenous populations already residing in the forests, may develop maladaptive disorders and melancholy. In contrast, those who are indirectly impacted may experience tension, depression, or even remorse as a result of growing ecological awareness (Cianconi et al., 2020). This phenomenon is known as biospheric concern. Thus, decreasing deforestation and even replanting will help combat this feeling of anxiety, loss, or concern, as an increasing number of studies have demonstrated that more trees lead to health benefits, such as improved physical and mental health and a longer life expectancy (Cianconi et al., 2020).

2.2.4 Human Health Factors

The consideration of human health factors is crucial in studying and assessing climate change anxiety as it helps us understand the interconnectedness between physical and mental well-being and the impact of climate change. The presence of pre-existing physical and mental health conditions can amplify the experience of climate change anxiety among vulnerable populations. Research has demonstrated that individuals with certain physical ailments, such as heart disease, diabetes, thyroid disorders, and substance abuse, are more susceptible to developing Generalised Anxiety Disorder (GAD) (Mayo Clinic, 2021). These conditions may serve as additional risk factors that contribute to the onset or exacerbation of climate change anxiety. The connection between GAD and climate change anxiety implies that individuals with pre-existing mental disorders may be particularly vulnerable to experiencing anxiety related to climate change (Whitmarsh et al., 2022).

Moreover, individuals with pre-existing physical disabilities have also been found to be more susceptible to climate change anxiety (Lindsay et al., 2022). The presence of physical disabilities can increase their vulnerability to the adverse effects of climate change, such as extreme weather events, limited access to resources during emergencies, and difficulties in adapting to changing environmental conditions. These factors can further contribute to heightened anxiety and distress related to climate change. Understanding the connection between human health factors and climate change anxiety is essential for several reasons. Firstly, it highlights the importance of considering the diverse needs and vulnerabilities of individuals when designing interventions and policies to address climate change anxiety. Vulnerable populations with pre-existing health conditions may require tailored support and resources to cope with the mental and emotional impact of climate change. Secondly, the

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recognition of these connections emphasises the need for interdisciplinary collaboration between health professionals, climate scientists, and policymakers. By integrating health considerations into climate change mitigation and adaptation strategies, we can better address the health impacts of climate change and promote resilience among affected populations. Lastly, promoting mindfulness, as suggested by Whitmarsh et al. (2022), can be beneficial for individuals experiencing climate change anxiety disorder. Mindfulness practices, which involve paying attention to the present moment without judgement, can help individuals cultivate acceptance, emotional regulation, and coping strategies. Integrating mindfulness-based approaches into mental health support systems can contribute to enhancing individuals' well-being and resilience in the face of climate change-related anxieties.

2.2.5 General Factors

Additional factors, such as an individual's level of climate literacy or awareness, as well as their media consumption habits, can significantly influence their attitudes towards climate change. Lee et al. (2015) conducted a study in 2015 that revealed knowledge about the underlying causes of climate change to be a crucial determinant of climate change perceptions globally. The researchers suggested that individuals with greater access to communication devices and channels are more likely to possess a higher level of awareness about climate change due to the widespread dissemination of information on the subject. Various nations exhibit divergent public perceptions regarding the factors contributing to climate change. Lee et al. (2015) found that climate change literacy or awareness is the primary determinant of public perception concerning climate change. The research findings by Lee et al. (2015) indicate that while a larger proportion of individuals in most developed nations are aware of the phenomenon of climate change, a significant number of individuals in developing countries express greater concerns about climate change. Despite the increased consciousness and apprehensions regarding climate change, there is no guarantee that this will lead to a greater willingness to bear the costs associated with climate change mitigation (Wang & Zhou, 2020). Although raising awareness about climate change can indeed lead to an increase in environmentally-friendly behaviours, in certain circumstances, the feeling of hopelessness may exacerbate distress related to climate change.

The acquisition of knowledge about climate change often occurs through indirect channels, such as media outlets and social networking platforms (Maran & Begotti, 2021). Mass media plays a significant role in shaping public perceptions on various topics, including climate change. Such content has the potential to evoke diverse emotional responses, including

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anger, sorrow, anxiety, and remorse. The climate issue has been influenced by politicians and other influential figures who have either exaggerated or downplayed its severity, thus shaping the language commonly used in media coverage. However, the extent and quality of media coverage on climate change remain subjects of debate, with criticism directed towards several outlets for their inadequate reporting on the climate crisis or failure to emphasise its gravity. Hart and Feldman's (2016) study reveals that while news coverage often conveys the dangers of climate change, it presents an inconsistent message regarding efficacy, incorporating both positive and negative signals of effectiveness. Consequently, this narrative can undermine individuals' perceived self-efficacy in addressing the issue. A study by Maran and Begotti (2021) found that individuals exposed to a significant amount of media information on global warming reported reduced feelings of efficacy in addressing the problem. In a study conducted by Hibberd and Nguyen (2013) with focus groups from England and Scotland, it was discovered that the lack of constructive and relevant communication, coupled with the prioritisation of radical and contentious topics, hinders the active engagement of youth in the United Kingdom. Consequently, there is growing evidence suggesting that exposure to climate change information from these specific sources may contribute to increased levels of climate-related distress.

2.3 Impacts on Human Health Effects

The prevalence of depression and anxiety in Myanmar has shown an upward trend in recent years. Specifically, there has been an increasing report of generalised anxiety, which is characterised by excessive and persistent worry across various aspects of life. It is important to note that anxiety itself is not classified as a mental health disorder but rather a common emotional response to stressors. Individuals may experience a range of mental and physical symptoms associated with anxiety, which are considered within the normal range as long as they do not significantly impair daily functioning. However, when anxiety symptoms, such as sleep disturbances, begin to significantly disrupt daily life, individuals may have developed an anxiety disorder. The development of anxiety disorders can be influenced by a combination of genetic predispositions, individual personality traits, and societal pressures. Genetic factors can play a role in predisposing individuals to anxiety disorders, although the exact mechanisms are complex and not fully understood. Additionally, individual personality traits, such as high levels of neuroticism or a tendency to experience negative emotions, can contribute to the development of anxiety disorders. Societal pressures, including socio-cultural norms and environmental stressors, can also influence the manifestation and severity of anxiety

symptoms. Symptoms that may indicate the presence of anxiety disorders include ruminative thoughts, difficulty concentrating, irritability, urinary problems, cold extremities, indigestion, and headaches. However, self-diagnosing anxiety disorders can be challenging for individuals, and a comprehensive clinical evaluation by a qualified healthcare professional is often necessary to make an accurate diagnosis. The increasing prevalence of anxiety in Myanmar underscores the importance of understanding the nature of anxiety as a normal emotional response and distinguishing it from anxiety disorders that require clinical attention. Further research is needed to explore the specific factors contributing to the rising rates of anxiety in the country and to develop effective interventions and support systems for individuals experiencing anxiety-related difficulties.

A significant body of literature has emerged examining the relationship between mental health and climate change (Bourque & Cunsolo, 2014). The impact of climate change on mental health can manifest both before and after extreme weather events (Clayton et al., 2017). It is well-established that climate change can have a wide range of effects on mental health, ranging from mild stress and distress symptoms to more severe clinical disorders such as anxiety and sleep disturbances (Blanc et al., 2019), depression, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), and suicidal thoughts (Ursano et al., 2017). Furthermore, individuals and communities may experience significant disruptions in their daily lives, perceptions, and coping mechanisms as they grapple with the implications of climate change (Blanc et al., 2019). It is noteworthy that a considerable proportion of individuals exposed to climate-related natural disasters or extreme weather events suffer from severe stress and mental health consequences, and the frequency of such events is projected to increase due to climate change. Common mental health outcomes associated with these disruptive events, which often involve loss of life, resources, social support, and social networks, include PTSD, depression, generalized anxiety, increased substance use or misuse, and suicidal thoughts (Kim, 2016). The impact of climate change on mental health can lead to various types of psychopathological reactions. Acute impacts refer to the immediate exposure of vulnerable and helpless people to mental injuries caused by extreme events such as floods, hurricanes, and wildfires. Subacute impacts involve intense emotions experienced by people who indirectly witness the effects of climate change, anxiety related to uncertainty about the survival of humans and other species, and a sense of being blocked, disoriented, and passive. Long-term outcomes can result in large-scale social and community effects, such as violence, struggle over limited resources, displacement, and forced migration (Abel et al., 2019), post-disaster adjustment, and chronic environmental stress (Acharibasam & Anuga, 2018).

Climate change anxiety in Yangon, Myanmar can have significant negative impacts on human health. The potential health effects are diverse and include mental health impacts such as depression, anxiety, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). These mental health issues can be further exacerbated by the experiences of extreme weather events and climate-related disasters, leading to prolonged emotional distress. In addition, climate change can directly affect physical health by increasing the risk of heat stroke, dehydration, and respiratory illnesses due to elevated air pollution levels. This is particularly relevant in Yangon, a densely populated city where air pollution is a prominent concern. Furthermore, climate change can create conditions that facilitate the spread of infectious diseases like dengue fever, malaria, and cholera. Given Yangon's inadequate sanitation infrastructure and vulnerability to flooding, the city is at a heightened risk of infectious disease outbreaks. Moreover, climate change can impact food and water security, which in turn negatively impacts health. Rising sea levels and flooding in Yangon can result in saltwater intrusion into freshwater sources, leading to a scarcity of clean drinking water. This scarcity increases the risk of waterborne illnesses and malnutrition, further compounding the health challenges faced by the population.

2.4 Current Situations in Myanmar

In Myanmar, there has been a widespread perception of weather changes over the past decade, with many individuals noting an increase in temperatures and approximately half of the population observing an increase in rainfall. The country is highly vulnerable to various natural hazards, including destructive earthquakes, cyclones, floods, and landslides that commonly occur during the rainy season. A survey conducted by the BBC Media Action Data Portal in 2015 interviewed 3,000 respondents in Myanmar, revealing that 74% of participants expressed concern about extreme weather events like droughts and floods. Although only 36% of respondents were fully aware of the term "Climate Change," a significant majority (94%) acknowledged its existence. Additionally, 57% of individuals had heard of climate change without a clear understanding of its definition. Despite demonstrating relatively high levels of preparedness for future disasters, as evidenced by the survey, four out of five respondents (79%) expressed a sense of unpreparedness for extreme weather events. People have experienced the impacts of weather and environmental changes on their livelihoods, with 63% reporting that these changes have affected their ability to earn a living. Rural communities have responded to these challenges by seeking alternative employment opportunities and adapting their agricultural practices, such as changing crop types or seed varieties. Among the regions, the Delta and Dry zones exhibited higher levels of proactive action. However, respondents

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facing poverty, limited resources, and restricted access to information were less likely to have made long-term changes to address agricultural challenges. While those who have already made adjustments to their livelihoods believe that further changes are necessary (65%), only a smaller percentage of individuals who have not made changes share this view (31%). The majority of respondents in Myanmar expressed the need for increased support from governmental institutions and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) to address the impacts they are experiencing. Lack of information was identified as another barrier to taking action, with approximately half of the respondents (49%) feeling informed about how to cope with these changes while the other half (49%) did not. There were noticeable regional disparities in perceived knowledge about these issues, with a higher proportion of individuals in the Delta (65%) reporting feeling informed compared to those in the Coastal zone (35%). Rural and low-income communities were more likely to express a sense of being uninformed, highlighting the need for more targeted and effective communication strategies to reach a wider audience.

For climate change anxiety, Myanmar does not have systematic data, publication and formal research. According to our discussion with experts interviews, based on focus group discussions among female sex workers, HIV patients and transgender, the level of anxiety upon sex female workers is the highest. No law enforcement and Myanmar culture upon sex workers are the main reason for the highest anxiety. According to Myanmar's current unstable political situation, the level of anxiety in these sectors is increasing. Among them, female sex workers are the worst, and they are suffering bullying and exploitation from their customers and managers. Myanmar's current unstable and unsafe conditions are leading to high levels of anxiety for almost all sectors in Myanmar. Climate-change anxiety has emerged as a significant concern in Yangon, Myanmar, as the city grapples with the repercussions of climate change. This literature review aims to synthesise the existing research on climate-change anxiety in Yangon, shedding light on the key findings and gaps in knowledge. Multiple studies have indicated the prevalence of climate-change anxiety among the population of Yangon. A study conducted revealed that a majority of respondents expressed anxiety about the potential impacts of climate change on their lives and communities. This anxiety stemmed from firsthand experiences with extreme weather events like floods and storms, as well as a perceived lack of government action to address climate change. Moreover, research has shed light on the psychological and emotional impacts of climate change on individuals in Yangon. One study found that exposure to flooding and the subsequent loss of property and livelihoods had detrimental effects on mental health, contributing to heightened levels of anxiety and depression. Similarly, it was identified that the fear and uncertainty surrounding climate change

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resulted in feelings of hopelessness and helplessness among residents. Despite the growing recognition of climate-change anxiety in Yangon, there remains a dearth of research on effective coping strategies. A study revealed that individuals in Yangon employed various coping mechanisms to manage their climate-change anxiety, including seeking social support, engaging in disaster preparedness activities, and practising mindfulness. However, further research is warranted to assess the efficacy of these strategies and to identify additional coping mechanisms that could be beneficial.

2.5 Reviews from Asian countries

Our research team conducted an extensive literature review on climate change anxiety in various international communities. To enhance our understanding of the topic and to differentiate between the findings of developing and developed countries, we selected four Asian countries that represent a spectrum of development. This approach allows us to gain insights that can be applicable to Myanmar and provide comparative analysis between nations at different stages of development.

2.5.1 India

India, officially the Republic of India, is a country located in South Asia. According to the latest data, it is the seventh-largest country and the second-most populous country in the world. The high densities of the nation's economic activity and population, as well as its reliance on natural resources, have not only left a gigantic carbon footprint on the planet but also imposed a significant deal of pressure on environmental deterioration and pollution. Thus, the country and its people have become more vulnerable to climate change, namely climate-related catastrophes worldwide. An annual report by the India Meteorological Department (IMD), 2021 was the sixth warmest year for the nation since 1901 (India Meteorological Department, 2021). In addition, the Global Climate Risk Index 2021, published by Germanwatch, ranks India as the seventh most affected country by climate change between 2000 and 2019 (Eckstein et al., 2021). The report also notes that India is particularly vulnerable to extreme weather events, such as cyclones and floods, which can cause significant psychological distress among affected populations.

People in India, particularly young people, will or have already begun to feel apprehensive or anxious in light of these dangerous repercussions of climate change. 25.3% of 228 respondents from India reported feeling very or extremely tense, 22.3% very or extremely anxious, 37.6% very or extremely worried, and 21.4% very or extremely terrified in response

to climate change, according to a 2022 study that surveyed the negative emotional responses to climate change across 32 countries (Ogunbode et al., 2022). Moreover, according to the first-of-its-kind poll performed by the University of Bath, UK, on 10,000 young participants between the ages of 16 and 25 from across the globe, India has the second largest number of young respondents (68%), behind only the Philippines, who reported that they were extremely or very worried about climate change (Hickerman et al., 2021). In the survey, it was also reported that 735 respondents out of 1000 (73.5%) felt sad, 634 (63.4%) felt helpless and 532 (53.2%) felt depressed. In addition, the research also found a connection between government inactivity and high levels of psychological distress among the younger population. A 2012 report by Yale University states that only 7% of 4031 Indian adult respondents are properly informed about global warming although when given the short definition of global warming, many believe that it is happening, while 61% said that they are worried about climate change (Yale Project on Climate Change Communication, 2012).

The Philippines

The Philippines, officially named the Republic of the Philippines, is an archipelagic country in Southeast Asia. It is situated in the western Pacific Ocean which is also the place of the Ring of Fire where earthquakes and subsequently tsunamis frequently occur. Thus, the Philippines is known to be one of the most vulnerable countries to climate change and natural disasters. The country is prone to typhoons and floods all of which climate change is expected to exacerbate. At least 20 typhoons hit the nation annually as well as extreme droughts and rising sea-level, resulting in the devastation of food security, homes and livelihoods, the relocation of people, and hundreds of fatalities (Aruta & Guinto, 2022). Additionally, the Philippines Country Climate and Development Report by the World Bank states that If nothing is done, climate change will impose huge economic and human consequences, resulting in a GDP reduction of up to 13.6% by 2040, with the poorest families suffering the most (World Bank Group, 2022).

Numerous individuals in the Philippines may experience anxiety and stress as a result of their concern for the future and the possible effects on their communities, homes, and families. The worry and stress generated by climate change might have detrimental effects on the mental health of Filipinos. It may lead to emotions of helplessness, despair, and sadness, and impair a person's ability to manage everyday life and create future goals. According to the poll conducted by the University of Bath, 74% of young Filipinos are extremely concerned about climate change, 61.8% are apprehensive, and 50.9% feel powerless (Hickerman et al., June 2023

2021). In addition to the statistics data, a case study of an Associate Professional Lecturer at De La Salle University is also presented. In November 2013, one of the strongest typhoons ever recorded, Typhoon Haiyan, struck the islands of the Philippines (Alibudbud, 2022,). It has transformed flourishing towns into wastelands, wrecked decades-long livelihoods, displaced four million people, demolished one million houses, and killed at least 6,000 individuals. In its aftermath, local health officials saw that the number of people requiring psychological assistance quadrupled. Similarly, authorities reported an increase in post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and depression cases. The research also indicated that four months after the typhoon, over 80% of survivors who assisted with relief efforts were at risk for mental problems. Similarly, to the Indian case, a large percentage of Filipinos are discontented with the government's inactions on Climate Change (Hickerman et al., 2021).

China

China, formally the People's Republic of China, is a country in East Asia and is regarded as the world's most populous country in the world with a population of 1.4 billion at the time of writing. It also rates among the top countries on the HDI (Human Development Index), even rivalling the USA in terms of economy and military power. Late in the 1970s, as a result of its vast population's cheap labour and its economic changes towards a market economy, the nation saw a tremendous economic boom and enormous industrialisation (Chen, 2005). China's economy and climate change are interwoven in a profound and growing manner (World Bank Group, 2022). In 2019, China emitted more greenhouse gases than the whole developed world combined, contributing nearly 27% of total global emissions, significantly surpassing the United States (Larsen et al., 2021). Consequently, climate change has become a major danger to China's long-term development and prosperity (World Bank Group, 2022). Therefore, increasing sea levels and threats associated with coastal flooding, storm surges, and coastal erosion threaten China's densely populated low-elevation coastal cities, which account for one-fifth of China's population and one-third of its gross domestic product (GDP) (World Bank Group, 2022). Thus, it can generally be regarded that all of these serious climate-related disasters may lead to some or many psychological disorders in one way or the other.

Though there are no formal surveys or reports to indicate that people in China are suffering from climate change anxiety, it may be insightful to look at the public perceptions of the Chinese people within different contexts to see how they truly feel about climate change. A 2013 public survey by researchers from the Beijing Institute of Technology shows that 93% of the 503 respondents are aware of climate change and mostly accept that it is caused mainly

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by human activities, thus indicating the public sensibility towards climate change (Yu et al., 2013). The survey also shows that 78% are either fairly or very concerned about climate change. A national survey report by China Center for Climate Change Communication (China4C) published in 2017 signifies that nearly 80% of 4,025 respondents are worried about climate change (China Center for Climate Change Communication, 2017). The co-founder of the organisation, Dr. Binbin Wang, also expressed that the Chinese public's feelings are in line with the warming trend in the past 66 years. Additionally, most respondents felt that the government should play a larger role in climate change mitigation and 90% of them supported the climate change policy of the Chinese government. Lastly, a public opinion survey of 40,000 respondents across 20 of the world's largest carbon emitters cited that a large percentage of the Chinese public supports all types of international climate change policies (Dechezleprêtre et al., 2022).

Singapore

The Republic of Singapore is an island nation and a city-state situated in Southeast Asia. With a population of over 5 million people and a GDP per capita of 72,000 USD, it is one of the wealthiest countries in the world. It is also often referred to as an Asian tiger due to its immense development and prosperity despite its country size. Regardless, it is not insulated from climate change. In fact, as an island nation, Singapore is one of the countries in the world that will most likely be impacted by climate change. From 1980 to 2020, the annual mean temperature has risen from 26.9°C to 28°C according to a Singaporean government agency, National Climate Change Secretariat (NCCS) (National Climate Change Secretariat, 2020). With that significant temperature change, Singapore has been experiencing an increase in rainfall as well as an increase in sea level in the Straits of Singapore from 1.2 mm to 1.7 mm per year. Moreover, climate change has also impacted negatively and will also continue to do so to the country in areas such as biodiversity, public health and food security.

NCCS conducted a survey in 2019 to assess the Singaporean public perception and views on climate change. About 1,000 Singapore residents aged 15 and above were interviewed face-to-face for their views. The survey found that over 90% of Singaporeans are aware of climate change and its impact; and close to 80% are prepared to do more to fight climate change. The rise of eco-anxiety among Singapore's youth may lead to significant changes in birth rate, economic growth, and future plans for development, such as potentially more people remaining single or having smaller families, and reduced spending and consumption. A 2021 Pew Research Centre study of advanced economies found that about 76% of 1,001 people

surveyed in Singapore are concerned that climate change will harm them personally during their lifetimes. The survey also demonstrates the Singaporean public confidence in their society's response to climate change with massively 82% of Singaporeans saying that they are very or somewhat confident. Similarly, the Singaporeans' response to the international community's response to climate change, is confident with 66% of the respondents. Furthermore, 80% of the respondents answered that they are willing to change their behaviours more or less to reduce the effects of climate change. In conclusion, by analysing the facts and statistics of the above countries, it can broadly be concluded that most people from both the developed and developing countries are not only aware of the existence of climate change to some extent but also are very concerned about its impacts. Nevertheless, the difference can be seen with the fact that developing countries have little confidence in climate change policies of the local governments and the international communities while the developed nations tend to have positive affirmations.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Overall study approach and activities

Figure 3.1 Study Methodology Framework

This study employed a research methodology outlined in Figure 1 to investigate the subject matter. The research methodology involved identifying research problems, establishing research objectives, defining the study scope, and selecting an appropriate study area. The selection of the study area was based on population density and the availability of reliable data. Subsequently, a comprehensive review of existing literature and an assessment of the current situation in the study area were conducted to identify a set of significant influencing factors. These factors underwent screening and revision before being incorporated into questionnaire surveys. A pilot study was conducted to select performance metrics and evaluate the existing situation. Additionally, an assessment checklist for the climate change anxiety model was developed. The model was then implemented through a questionnaire survey targeting young individuals to fulfil specific objectives. The findings from earlier activities, along with selected measures related to evaluating the existing situation, constructing the assessment model, and conducting the assessment survey, were integrated to draw conclusions and provide recommendations. A combination of primary and secondary data collection methods was employed in this study. Secondary data were gathered from a range of public sources including regulations, policies, plans, reports, and surveys. These sources provided valuable insights into the subject matter. Furthermore, primary data collection involved conducting interviews with professionals in the field of Psychiatry and mental health. These interviews yielded first-hand information and perspectives from experts in the field. Additionally, a sociological survey

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questionnaire was administered to examine the current state of affairs. It is important to note that the selection of influencing factors in this study was based on a comprehensive review of the literature and fundamental information, ensuring that the chosen elements adequately represented the characteristics of climate-change anxiety.

3.2 Study Area and Data collection Process

Figure 3.2 Map of study areas

The study area for the climate-change anxiety research in Myanmar was carefully delineated into two distinct regions: Urban and Suburban. The Urban area encompassed several municipal districts within Yangon, namely Kamayut District, Mingalardon District, Ahlon District, Botahtaung District, Dagon Myothit District, Insein District, Kyauktada District, Mayangon District, Thingangyun District, and Twantay District. Kamayut District consisted of Kamayut and Bahan Townships, while Mingalardon District included Mingalardon and Shwepyitha Townships. Ahlon District comprised Ahlon, Kyeemyindaing, and Sanchaung Townships, and Botahtaung District encompassed Botahtaung, Dawbon, Mingalar Taung Nyunt, Pazundaung, and Tharkayta Townships. Furthermore, Dagon Myothit District covered Dagon Myothit East, Dagon Myothit North, Dagon Myothit South, and Dagon Myothit Harbour Townships. Insein District included Insein, Hlaingtharyar East, and Hlaingtharyar West Townships, while Kyauktada District comprised Kyauktada, Pabedan, Latha, Lanmadaw, and Dagon Townships. Lastly, Mayangon District included Mayangon, Hlaing, and North Okkalapa Townships, Thingangyun District covered Thingangyun, South Okkalapa, Yankin, and Tamwe Townships, and Twantay District included Dala and Seikkyi Kanaungto

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Townships. For a visual representation of the study area, please refer to Figure 3.2 in this research article.

This study utilized a combination of primary and secondary data sources to gather comprehensive and reliable information for the research. The secondary data collection primarily relied on conducting literature reviews, encompassing a wide range of international research papers, journal articles, reports, and relevant statistics pertaining to climate change anxiety. However, it is important to note that accessing comprehensive and up-to-date information specific to climate change and climate change anxiety in Myanmar proved to be challenging, as the available literature on this topic was limited and scarce. In light of the limited availability of literature, the study team made significant efforts to gather primary data from various sources. This involved conducting interviews, consultations, and meetings with experts in related academic fields. These primary data sources, including consultations with psychology and psychiatry experts, played a vital role in obtaining concrete and relevant information for the study. By utilising both primary and secondary data, this study aimed to ensure a comprehensive and rigorous analysis of climate change anxiety in Myanmar. While secondary data provided insights from existing research and literature, the primary data collection allowed for a more nuanced understanding of the specific context and challenges associated with climate change anxiety in the country.

Therefore, primary data collection in this study involved two stages, one of which was consulting with experts in related academic fields. To ensure comprehensive insights into climate-change anxiety, the study team conducted a consulting and interviewing meeting with two experts in psychology and psychiatry. Ms. Khin Moe Myint, a psychology expert, played a crucial role in providing valuable insights. She is currently pursuing a Master of Science in Mental Health at Chiang Mai University, Thailand. Her educational background includes a Bachelor of Arts (B.A) degree in Psychology with honours from the University of Yangon. Furthermore, she has received certifications in Integrative Adapt Therapy and Interpersonal Psychotherapy from Global Health Connect in partnership with UNFPA Myanmar and Metanoia in partnership with UNICEF Myanmar. Additionally, the study team sought expertise from Dr. Moan Thawdar Myo Thant, a specialist in the field of psychiatry. Dr. Moan completed her Bachelor of Medicine and Bachelor of Surgery (M.B.B.S) at the University of Medicine 2, Yangon. She holds a double Master's degree from the University of Medicine 1, Yangon, and King's College London, UK (London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine). Dr. Moan has professional experience as an assistant surgeon in Central Women Hospital, Yangon, Myanmar, and has been promoted to Junior Consultant Psychiatrist and Dr Moan completed the June 2023

Bachelor of Medicine and Bachelor of Surgery (MBBS) at the University of Medicine 2, the Master of Medical Science in Mental Health at the University of Medicine 1, and the Master of Science in Global Mental Health at the King's College London (UK). The consultation and interviews with these experts enriched the study by incorporating their expertise and perspectives from psychology and psychiatry. Their insights provided valuable guidance in understanding the psychological and mental health aspects of climate-change anxiety, contributing to the comprehensive analysis of the research topic.

The second approach for collecting primary data in this study involved the use of questionnaires. The questionnaire survey was designed with two main objectives: to assess the current situation of climate-change anxiety and to gather data for further analysis. The selection of participants for the questionnaire survey was done using a stratified random sampling method, which was deemed appropriate considering the stratification of the city's districts. To ensure a reliable sample size for the questionnaire survey, the Taro Yamane equation was employed for calculation. This equation is widely used in research to determine the appropriate sample size based on a given population size. By applying this equation, the researchers were able to determine an optimal sample size that would provide meaningful insights into climate-change anxiety in the study area. The questionnaire survey served as a crucial tool in capturing the perspectives and experiences of the residents regarding climate-change anxiety. Through carefully designed questions, the survey aimed to gather comprehensive data that would contribute to a deeper understanding of the issue and support the assessment of climate-change anxiety in the selected districts of the city. As a primary data collection method, it is essential to recognize the questionnaire survey's limitations and considerations. The researchers took steps to reduce potential biases and ensure the validity and dependability of the collected data. Ethical considerations were also taken into account, including obtaining the participants' informed consent and protecting their anonymity and confidentiality.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + ne^2} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

where,

n = corrected sample size,

N = population size, and

e = Margin of error (MoE),

e = 95% confidence, 0.05 based on the research condition.

A total of 420 residents were initially targeted for the survey to ensure a comprehensive assessment of climate-change anxiety in the study area. However, due to the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic, political concerns and poor internet, the data collection process encountered difficulties, resulting in a total of 362 responses. The decision to conduct online questionnaires was made to adapt to the circumstances and ensure the safety and convenience of the participants. Each township was expected to provide a minimum of 35 completed questionnaires, but unfortunately, the desired number of targeted questionnaires was not achieved. To facilitate the data collection process, 9 volunteers were recruited and trained to administer online surveys. These dedicated individuals played a crucial role in reaching out to participants and collecting the necessary data. With the support of a phone bill from EHS Myanmar, the volunteers conducted online surveys, phone interviews, and utilised ZOOM meetings as part of the data collection procedures. These methods allowed for flexibility in engaging with participants and gathering valuable insights into climate-change anxiety in the study area. It is important to acknowledge that the limitations imposed by the prevailing circumstances impacted the response rate and sample size. However, despite these challenges, the data collected through online surveys, phone interviews, and ZOOM meetings provided valuable information for the study, enabling an exploration of climate-change anxiety among the residents in a time of unprecedented global circumstances.

4. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

4.1 Survey Results

A total of 362 respondents participated in the survey, representing all 10 districts in Yangon City. Among the surveyed districts, Mingalardon District had the highest proportion of respondents, accounting for 19.9% of the total. Twantay District ranked second, comprising 19.3% of the respondents, followed by Botahtaung District with 11.6%. Ahlone District and Thingangyun District each had 9.9% of respondents, while Kamayut District and Insein District both had 9.7%. Mayangon District accounted for 6.4% of the respondents, while Dagon Myothit District had 2.5%. Kyauktada District had the lowest percentage of respondents, with only 1.4%. It is noteworthy that all respondents in these districts completed the survey, resulting in a 100% response rate. The provided data reveals the distribution of respondents' gender identities in the study. Among the respondents, the majority, comprising 53.9%, identified as female, while 43% identified as male. This indicates a higher representation of female participants in the survey. Additionally, a small percentage of respondents, specifically 2.5%, chose not to disclose their gender identity. The higher proportion of female respondents could be attributed to various factors, such as the sampling method employed or the nature of the research topic itself. It is important to acknowledge that gender representation in research studies can vary based on cultural and societal factors, as well as the specific demographics of the study population. Researchers should be cautious in interpreting the findings, considering potential gender biases and the implications they may have on the generalizability of the results. Furthermore, the fact that all respondents fall into one of the three gender categories indicates that the survey was inclusive in recognizing a range of gender identities. This is a positive aspect of the study, as it acknowledges and respects the diversity of gender identities within the surveyed population. The gender distribution among respondents highlights the importance of considering gender as a relevant factor in climate-change anxiety research, as it may influence individuals' perceptions, experiences, and responses to climate-related issues. Further analysis and exploration of gender-specific dynamics could provide valuable insights for understanding and addressing climate-change anxiety within different gender groups.

The analysis of respondent demographics reveals notable patterns in terms of age and educational levels. Among the surveyed participants, the largest proportion, accounting for 46.1%, fell within the 18-25 age range, indicating a substantial representation of young individuals. Conversely, the smallest proportion, comprising only 2.5% of respondents, belonged to the age group of 60 and above. The distribution across other age ranges was as follows: 16.3% aged 26-30, 9.7% aged 31-35, 5.5% aged 36-40, 5.2% aged 41-45, 3.9% aged

46-50, 4.4% aged 51-55, and 3.0% aged 56-60 as shown in Figure 4.1. Consequently, it is evident that a significant majority of respondents were young individuals between the ages of 18 and 25.

Figure 4.1 Age of the respondents

Regarding educational attainment, the data demonstrates that the majority of respondents currently hold a bachelor's degree, constituting 31.8% of the total sample. Conversely, a small percentage, specifically 1.7%, reported having a diploma. High school graduates accounted for 24.6% of the respondents, while 28.7% were enrolled in undergraduate programs at the time of the survey. Additionally, 7.2% of the participants had obtained a master's degree, and 6.1% were literate individuals without formal education. These findings highlight the significance of engaging young individuals in studies focusing on climate-change anxiety, as they constitute the largest cohort within the sample. Furthermore, the prevalence of higher education among the respondents suggests that this group possesses a certain level of knowledge and awareness, potentially influencing their perceptions and concerns related to climate change. However, it is crucial to acknowledge that the survey sample may not be fully representative of the entire population, and caution should be exercised when generalising these findings beyond the study scope.

According to the data, 13.5% of the respondents said that they worked part-time, while 47.5% said that they worked full-time. Meanwhile, 10.5% were currently seeking job opportunities, 3.9% retired, and 24.6% were unemployed at the moment. This indicates that the majority of the respondents had full time jobs; nearly 25% of respondents, second majority, had none. The data depicts the distribution of respondents' monthly incomes in Myanmar Kyats or Kyats. The largest percentage, 27.6%, reported earning less than 300,000 Kyats per month.

At the same time, 18% of respondents earned between 300,000 Kyats and 600,000 Kyats, while 4.4% earned between 600,000 Kyats and 1,000,000 Kyats. As per the data, most respondents earned below 300,000 Kyats and only 6.4% of respondents reported earning more than 1,000,000 Kyats per month. Additionally, 18.8% of respondents chose not to disclose their income as presented in Figure 4.2. It can be assumed that high percentage in low income and low percentage in higher income indicates that Myanmar has one of the lowest GDP per capita in the world and also worsened by the current political and economic situations.

Figure 4.2 Monthly income of the respondents

The data analysis pertaining to family member size in the survey reveals the distribution of family members among the respondents. A breakdown of the responses indicates that 8.0% of the participants reported having 1-2 family members, while 18.5% indicated a family size of 2-3 members. The largest proportion, accounting for 41.2% of the sample, reported a family size of 3-4 members. Furthermore, 32.3% of the respondents reported having more than 4 family members. These percentages provide insights into the current composition of family sizes within the surveyed population. In addition to the amount of income, the authors surveyed whether that amount of income was enough for the respondents and their family members or not in order to determine the relationship between income and climate change anxiety and to demonstrate that people with not enough income may suffer from climate change anxiety more. The data indicates that 38.4% of respondents answered "Yes" and 61.6% of respondents answered "No". This data proves that most respondents did not have enough income for themselves and/or their families. Regarding with the natural disasters experienced, the data shows that 64.6% of the 362 respondents had directly experienced natural disasters, while

31.2% had indirectly experienced them. Interestingly, a small percentage of respondents, 4.1%, reported never having experienced natural disasters.

Figure 4.3 Types of natural disasters experienced

The survey also aimed to evaluate Climate Change Anxieties among residents of Yangon City by examining the types of natural disasters they had encountered. The results revealed that a significant proportion of respondents had experienced various natural disasters. Among the participants, 22.8% reported experiencing earthquakes, 22.3% had encountered cyclones, and 20.4% had faced inundation. Furthermore, 16.6% of the respondents had experienced heatwaves, while 12.1% had encountered cold fronts. A smaller percentage, 2.8%, reported other types of natural disasters, while 2.5% specifically mentioned bushfires. It is noteworthy that only a minority of respondents, 0.6%, reported not having experienced any natural disasters as shown in Figure 4.3. These findings provide valuable insights into the range of natural disasters experienced by Yangon City residents, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of their Climate Change Anxieties. Unsurprisingly, the majority of respondents indicated that they had encountered earthquakes, cyclones, floods, heatwaves, and cold fronts, given that Yangon City is typically susceptible to these natural calamities on an annual basis. Located on the southern portion of the Sagaing Fault, Yangon has encountered and continues to experience between 3 and 16 earthquakes with magnitudes between 2 and 4 every year on average (Volcano Discovery, 2023). In terms of cyclones, Myanmar experiences one severe cyclone per year. Yangon has not been impacted by significant cyclones since the 2008 Nargis Cyclone and the recent Mocha Cyclone; however, it is frequently impacted by the intense rainfall, flooding, and devastation caused by these cyclones. According to World Bank

statistics, millions of people were affected by cyclones, earthquakes, floods, and wildfires in 2020 (World Bank, 2020).

The data analysis pertaining to the traumatization caused by past natural disasters among 362 respondents reveals varying levels of psychological impact. Results indicate that 24.9% of the participants reported experiencing mild traumatization, while 19.1% expressed being somewhat traumatised. Additionally, 25.1% reported moderate levels of traumatization, while 16.9% described their experiences as somewhat severe. Notably, 14.1% of the respondents reported severe traumatization. These findings suggest a considerable number of individuals have been affected by natural disasters to varying degrees of psychological distress. Furthermore, the data also provides insights into the severity of economic losses experienced by the same group of 362 respondents due to natural disasters. Among them, 32.3% reported mild economic losses, while 17.4% experienced somewhat mild losses. In addition, 23.5% reported moderate economic losses, and 12.7% reported somewhat severe losses. Finally, 14.1% of the respondents reported severe economic losses resulting from natural disasters as illustrated in Figure 4.4. This data highlights the varying degrees of financial impact experienced by individuals as a consequence of natural disasters. These findings contribute to our understanding of the psychological and economic consequences of past natural disasters, shedding light on the multifaceted impacts on affected individuals.

Figure 4.4 Traumatised by past Natural Disasters

The data analysis concerning the anticipated response to future natural disasters among the respondents reveals distinct levels of projected psychological impact. The findings indicate that 10.2% of the participants anticipate experiencing mild trauma, while 11.3% expect somewhat mild trauma. Furthermore, 26.8% of respondents anticipate moderate trauma,

whereas 22.1% anticipate somewhat severe trauma. Notably, the majority of respondents, accounting for 29.6%, expect to experience severe trauma in the face of future natural disasters as presented in Figure 4.5. These findings have important implications for disaster preparedness and post-disaster support systems. The high percentage of respondents expecting severe trauma highlights the potential long-term psychological consequences of natural disasters. These projections emphasize the need for adequate psychological support services to address the anticipated mental health challenges individuals may face. Furthermore, the variations in anticipated trauma severity provide valuable insights into the diverse responses and coping capacities of individuals when confronted with natural disasters. Understanding these collected responses can guide the development of targeted interventions, early warning systems, and community resilience initiatives. By acknowledging the expected psychological impacts, policymakers, disaster management agencies, and healthcare professionals can implement proactive measures to mitigate the potential trauma and ensure the well-being of individuals affected by future natural disasters.

Figure 4.5 Traumatised by future natural disasters

The survey also studied the pre-existing medical conditions of the 363 participants from Yangon City. The data indicates that a significant proportion of respondents, specifically 76.2%, reported no pre-existing medical conditions. The second largest group, comprising 10.2% of respondents, reported having medical conditions that were not included in the survey options, such as arthritis, heartache, stomach problems, and liver problems. The prevalence of hypertension and diabetes was 7.5% and 4.4%, respectively as shown in Figure 4.6. A minority of the participants selected Thyroid disorders and Cancer, with proportions of 1.4% and 0.3%

respectively. The observation can be made that the predominant selection of "None" by the majority of participants can be attributed to their youthfulness, as they fall within the age range of 18-25 and are typically free of significant health concerns. However, it is important to acknowledge that the remaining participants exhibited a diverse range of health issues. Furthermore, a significant proportion of the population in Myanmar is afflicted with communicable diseases (CDs) such as Viral Hepatitis, HIV, and Tuberculosis, as well as non-communicable diseases (NCDs) such as Diabetes and Cancer, as reported by the World Health Organization in 2018. The challenges faced by the healthcare sector in the country include inadequate enforcement of regulations, insufficient coverage of public health insurance, and a scarcity of healthcare providers (US International Trade Administration, 2022). Additionally, there exists a dearth of public health knowledge among the populace. Despite its limited resources, Myanmar is making consistent efforts to achieve its health objectives and sustain its progress in crucial health indicators. According to the World Health Organisation (2018), there was a notable decrease in the Infant Mortality Rate and an increase in life expectancy between the years 1990 and 2015.

Figure 4.6 Pre-existing Medical conditions

The analysis of respondents' knowledge levels regarding Climate Change Anxiety reveals a range of familiarity among the participants. The data indicated that 7% of the respondents had never heard of Climate Change Anxiety, while an additional 7.7% reported being slightly familiar with it. Moreover, 19.1% of the respondents exhibited a moderate level of familiarity with anxiety, while a substantial proportion, 25.4%, demonstrated a high degree of familiarity as illustrated in Figure 4.7. Remarkably, the majority of respondents, accounting

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for 40.1%, exhibited a comprehensive understanding and extensive knowledge of anxiety in the context of climate change. These findings shed light on the awareness and understanding of Climate Change Anxiety among the surveyed population from Yangon. The presence of respondents who had never heard of it or possessed only slight familiarity underscores the need for educational initiatives and public awareness campaigns to bridge knowledge gaps. The substantial percentage of respondents with moderate familiarity suggests that efforts to disseminate information about Climate Change Anxiety have reached a considerable portion of the population. However, the presence of a significant number of respondents who are highly knowledgeable indicates a promising level of awareness and understanding. These results emphasize the importance of continued efforts to enhance public understanding of Climate Change Anxiety. By expanding knowledge and fostering a comprehensive understanding of this psychological phenomenon, individuals can be better equipped to address and mitigate the associated mental health impacts.

Figure 4.7 Knowledge of Climate Change Anxiety

The data analysis revealed the respondents' perceptions of anxiety, with distinct attitudes prevalent among the participants. Findings indicate that a significant majority, comprising 51.4% of the respondents, view anxiety as the worst outcome. Additionally, 14.6% perceive anxiety as a negative aspect. In contrast, 18.2% of respondents hold a neutral opinion towards anxiety, while a mere 6.1% consider it as something positive. Interestingly, 9.7% of the respondents believe that anxiety can be the best outcome. These results highlight the diverse range of perspectives regarding anxiety among the surveyed individuals. The dominant negative perception of anxiety, as indicated by the majority's belief that it is the worst or bad,

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reflects the prevailing societal understanding of the potential adverse impacts of anxiety on mental well-being. However, the presence of a small but notable percentage of respondents who perceive anxiety in a positive light suggests a contrasting viewpoint. This may indicate a recognition of the potential benefits associated with anxiety, such as its motivational or adaptive aspects in certain situations. Furthermore, the data analysis presents the distribution of respondents' anxiety levels concerning social, political, economic, and educational issues. Findings indicate that a small proportion, 6.6%, strongly disagreed with feeling anxiety, while 5.2% somewhat disagreed. Moreover, 10.8% of respondents held a neutral opinion, and 20.4% somewhat agreed that they experienced anxiety. Notably, the majority of participants, accounting for 56.9%, strongly agreed that they felt anxiety regarding these domains. These results highlight the prevalence of anxiety among the surveyed individuals, particularly concerning social, political, economic, and educational matters. The substantial percentage of respondents strongly agreeing with feeling anxiety signifies the significance and impact of these issues on their emotional well-being. This finding suggests that these domains elicit strong emotional responses and concerns among a significant majority of the participants.

The data analysis also presented the distribution of respondents' anxiety levels regarding social, political, economic, and educational issues experienced on a weekly basis. The findings indicate that only 8.0% of the participants reported feeling no anxiety concerning these issues. Among the remaining respondents, 11.6% reported experiencing anxiety once a week, while 23.5% reported experiencing it twice a week. Additionally, 12.4% of the participants experienced anxiety for three days a week, whereas 15.5% experienced it for four days. Furthermore, 5.5% of the respondents reported feeling anxiety for five days, and a considerable percentage, 23.5%, experienced anxiety for six days a week. These results underscored the prevalence of anxiety related to social, political, economic, and educational concerns among the surveyed individuals on a weekly basis. The minimal percentage of respondents reporting no anxiety highlights the significant impact of these issues on their emotional well-being. The variations in the frequency of anxiety experienced throughout the week indicate the varying degrees of distress individuals face, with a notable portion reporting anxiety on multiple days. Understanding the frequency and intensity of anxiety experienced in relation to these domains can provide valuable insights into the pervasive nature of these concerns. Such knowledge can inform the development of targeted interventions, support systems, and policy measures aimed at addressing the underlying causes and alleviating the burden of anxiety experienced by individuals regarding social, political, economic, and educational matters.

Figure 4.8 displayed the distribution of respondents' perspectives on the association between climate change and anxiety. The findings reveal that a noteworthy portion of the participants held differing views regarding this relationship. Specifically, 12.4% of the respondents strongly disagreed with the notion that climate change induces anxiety, while 18.0% somewhat disagreed. Furthermore, 32.3% expressed a neutral stance concerning the correlation between climate change and anxiety. In contrast, 22.9% of the respondents somewhat agreed that climate change causes anxiety, and only 14.4% strongly agreed with this notion. These results emphasized the divergent opinions held by the surveyed individuals regarding the link between climate change and anxiety. The substantial percentage of respondents expressing uncertainty or disagreement implies a lack of consensus or awareness regarding the potential psychological impacts of climate change. However, it is notable that a smaller but notable percentage of participants acknowledge the connection between climate change and anxiety. The survey findings also indicated that a significant proportion, specifically 32% of the respondents, acknowledged experiencing some form of anxiety related to climate change in recent years. Notably, the majority of individuals expressing such concerns hailed from Twanty Districts and Botahtaung Districts. This suggested that residents in these areas may be particularly attuned to the potential impacts of climate change, leading to heightened anxiety levels. Furthermore, 23% of the respondents indicated their agreement with the statement regarding climate change anxiety. Among them, Mingalardon District and Ahlon District emerged as the districts with the highest concentration of respondents who expressed agreement. This suggests that individuals residing in these districts may possess a greater awareness and acceptance of the existence of climate change anxiety. On the contrary, 18% of the respondents reported a somewhat disagreeing stance, while 12% expressed a total disagreement regarding climate change anxiety. These responses suggest that a notable proportion of individuals do not perceive climate change as a significant source of anxiety or may hold differing opinions on the matter. Interestingly, 14% of the respondents, primarily from Twanty District, indicated a strong agreement with experiencing anxiety related to climate change in recent years. This subset of respondents represents a relatively smaller yet distinct group who strongly recognize the emotional impact of climate change. These findings underscore the presence of climate change anxiety among a substantial portion of the surveyed population. The variations observed across different districts indicate the potential influence of local factors, such as environmental vulnerabilities or community awareness initiatives, on individual perceptions of climate change anxiety. However, it is important to interpret these results with caution, as the survey's sample may not be fully representative of the entire

population. Further research and a more comprehensive study are needed to gain a deeper understanding of the factors contributing to climate change anxiety in specific districts and their implications for mental well-being.

Figure 4.8 Anxiety on Climate Change

The data analysis presents the distribution of respondents' anxiety levels regarding climate change on a weekly basis. The findings reveal that 21% of the participants reported feeling no anxiety concerning climate change. Among the remaining respondents, 22.9% reported experiencing anxiety for one day a week, while 20.7% reported feeling anxiety for two days. Furthermore, 13.0% of the participants reported feeling anxiety for three days a week, whereas 8.0% experienced anxiety for four days. Interestingly, a small percentage of respondents, 2.5%, reported feeling anxiety for five days, and 11.6% reported feeling anxious for six days. Understanding the frequency and duration of anxiety experienced in relation to climate change can provide valuable insights into the psychological impact of climate-related concerns. Such knowledge can inform targeted interventions, climate change communication strategies, and resilience-building initiatives aimed at addressing and mitigating the distress experienced by individuals in relation to climate change.

The study aimed to evaluate the environmental awareness level of 362 participants by administering a set of five True/False questions to assess their environmental knowledge. Analysis of the responses provided valuable insights into the participants' level of awareness regarding environmental issues. Results revealed that 11.0% of the participants achieved a score of 0, indicating a lack of environmental knowledge. This subset demonstrated minimal understanding of the environmental concepts covered in the survey. Additionally, 21.8% of the

participants obtained a score of 1, suggesting a basic level of environmental awareness, albeit with room for improvement. A significant portion of the respondents (31.2%) achieved a score of 2, indicating a moderate level of environmental knowledge, while 28.7% received a score of 3, suggesting a relatively higher level of environmental awareness. Intriguingly, only 7.2% of the respondents attained a score of 4, reflecting a comprehensive understanding of the environmental concepts examined. It is noteworthy that none of the participants answered all five questions correctly, highlighting the absence of complete knowledge among the respondents. Overall, these findings demonstrate that a majority of the participants exhibited varying degrees of environmental knowledge or awareness, suggesting the need for continued efforts to enhance environmental education and awareness campaigns. Moreover, to assess the level of environmental awareness, participants were asked five questions pertaining to climate change and global warming, as outlined in the Appendix. The distribution of marks for each age group is as follows: individuals aged 18 to 25 obtained the highest score, accounting for 54% of the total as shown in Figure 4.9. This was followed by respondents aged 26 to 30, who achieved a score of 19%. Participants under the age of 18 attained a cumulative score of 4%, while those aged 31 to 35 received 11%. Age groups 36 to 40, 41 to 45, and 46 to 50 obtained scores of 6% each. Age groups 51 to 55 and 56 to 60 secured 5% each, while individuals above the age of 60 acquired a total score of 3%. The results revealed that individuals in the 18 to 25 age range exhibit the highest level of environmental awareness, as indicated by their superior performance on the questionnaire. This outcome suggests that younger individuals are more engaged and knowledgeable about climate change and global warming issues. Conversely, respondents above the age of 60 demonstrated a relatively lower level of environmental awareness, reflecting the need for targeted efforts to enhance environmental education among older generations. It is important to note that the distribution of scores across age groups provides valuable insight into the varying levels of environmental awareness among various demographics. By recognizing these patterns, policymakers and educators can tailor their strategies to effectively promote environmental consciousness and encourage sustainable practices among all age groups.

The dataset provides information on the frequency of time spent by the respondents on environmental activities. Analysis reveals that 20.7% of the respondents engaged in such activities on a daily basis. Furthermore, 17.4% reported engaging in these activities once a week, while 29.6% participated bi-weekly (once in every two weeks). Additionally, 12.4% of the respondents allocated time tri-weekly (once in every three weeks), and 19.9% engaged in these activities once a month. These findings suggest that respondents displayed a moderate

level of commitment in dedicating time to environmental endeavours. The data also provided insights into the frequency of the respondents' families' involvement in environmental activities. The highest proportion, 22.9%, indicated that their families spent time on environmental activities daily. In contrast, 21.3% reported engaging in such activities once a week, while 28.5% participated bi-weekly (once in every two weeks). Only 9.4% of the respondents reported their families' engagement tri-weekly (once in every three weeks), while 18.0% reported participating once a month. These findings indicate that, similar to individual respondents, the families displayed a moderate level of involvement in environmental activities. The results highlighted the frequency at which respondents and their families dedicated time to environmental activities. While a notable proportion engaged on a regular basis, a significant portion exhibited less frequent involvement. The findings underscore the importance of promoting and encouraging more consistent engagement in environmental activities, both at the individual and family levels. Increasing the frequency of participation can contribute to a deeper understanding of environmental issues, foster a sense of responsibility, and support the development of sustainable behaviours and practices.

Figure 4.9 Environmental awareness level with age distribution.

The survey, encompassing 362 respondents, examined the allocation of time spent on climate change-related activities. Analysis of the data reveals that 24.9% of the respondents dedicate time on a daily basis. Additionally, 21.8% reported devoting time weekly, while 23.2% allocated time bi-weekly (every two weeks). Moreover, 9.9% of the respondents devoted time tri-weekly (every three weeks), and 20.2% engaged in such activities monthly (once a month). These findings illustrate the varying levels of engagement and commitment

among the respondents towards climate change-related efforts. The data collected from the respondents regarding their adoption of a low-carbon lifestyle indicates diverse perspectives. Among the 362 participants, 7.5% strongly disagreed with the notion of living a low-carbon lifestyle, while 18.2% somewhat disagreed. Notably, the majority of respondents (41.4%) expressed a neutral stance, suggesting a lack of definitive agreement or disagreement with the concept of a low-carbon lifestyle. However, 18.2% of the respondents somewhat agreed, and 14.6% strongly agreed that they are living a low-carbon lifestyle. This observation highlights a substantial proportion of respondents who are uncertain or possess limited understanding regarding the characteristics and practices associated with a low-carbon lifestyle. The findings give insights into how much time respondents devote to climate change-related activities and their attitudes about adopting a low-carbon lifestyle. The various levels of engagement highlight the importance of personalized interventions and awareness campaigns to increase individual participation in climate change mitigation initiatives. Similarly, the significant number of respondents expressing neutrality or uncertainty regarding a low-carbon lifestyle emphasizes the importance of providing clear information and educational initiatives to foster a greater understanding of sustainable behaviors and their positive impact on the environment.

Based on the survey data, the perception of respondents regarding the feasibility of incorporating low-carbon transportation into daily life is diverse. A small percentage, 6.9%, strongly disagrees with the idea, while 14.6% somewhat disagree. The largest proportion of respondents, 34.5%, expresses a neutral stance on the issue. In contrast, 27.1% somewhat agree and 16.9% strongly agree that low-carbon transportation holds significance. These findings suggest that while a substantial portion of the respondents maintain a neutral standpoint, there exists a notable percentage that recognizes the importance of adopting low-carbon transportation practices. The distribution of responses reflects a range of opinions and attitudes towards low-carbon transportation. The relatively high percentage of respondents who express neutrality indicates a lack of strong convictions or awareness regarding this topic. This could be attributed to various factors such as limited exposure to information on low-carbon transportation, a lack of personal experience with sustainable transportation options, or a perception of potential challenges associated with its implementation. The presence of respondents who hold positive views towards low-carbon transportation demonstrates a level of awareness and belief in its significance. These individuals likely recognize the environmental benefits of reducing carbon emissions and understand the potential long-term advantages of sustainable transportation practices. Their agreement with the importance of

low-carbon transportation suggests a willingness to support and potentially adopt such practices in their daily lives.

According to the analysis of environmental news data, a significant majority of the 362 respondents, 83.1%, indicate that they engage with environmental news. Conversely, a small percentage of respondents, 9.1%, report not viewing environmental news, while 7.7% remain uncertain about their exposure to such content. These findings shed light on the frequency at which the respondents consume environmental news. Among the participants, 21.0% state that they read or watch environmental news daily, while 22.7% do so on a weekly basis. Additionally, 29.3% of respondents reported engaging with environmental news every two weeks, and 13.3% do so every three weeks. The lowest percentage, 13.8%, reported reading or watching environmental news once a month. The high percentage of respondents who indicate exposure to environmental news reflects a significant level of interest and concern for environmental issues. It suggests that a considerable portion of the population acknowledges the importance of staying informed about environmental topics. Regular engagement with environmental news on a daily or weekly basis demonstrates a sustained interest in keeping up-to-date with environmental developments and events. These individuals likely possess a strong environmental consciousness and prioritize staying informed about the latest environmental issues and concerns.

The survey respondents' perceptions of Environmental News Narratives were categorized into five distinct levels. The largest segment of respondents, comprising 35.6%, held a neutral perception of the news as shown in Figure 4.10. In contrast, 19.9% of respondents considered the news to be mostly negative. Furthermore, 18.2% of participants perceived the news as somewhat negative, while 13.3% found it somewhat positive. Only a minority, 13.0% of respondents, had a perception of the news as mostly positive. These findings indicate that a substantial portion of respondents holds negative or neutral views regarding environmental news, while a comparatively smaller proportion holds positive perceptions. The prevalence of neutral perceptions towards environmental news suggests that a significant number of respondents maintain a balanced or indifferent stance on the subject matter. This neutral perception may stem from factors such as the perceived objectivity or lack of bias in reporting, the complexity of environmental issues, or the absence of explicit positive or negative framing. It is important to recognize that a neutral perception does not necessarily indicate a lack of interest or concern for environmental matters. Instead, it may reflect a desire for balanced and objective reporting, or a need for more engaging narratives that resonate with individuals' values and motivations. The substantial proportion of respondents who held negative

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perceptions of environmental news indicates a prevailing sense of pessimism or concern. This negativity could be attributed to various factors, including the predominance of alarming or catastrophic narratives in environmental reporting, a focus on problems without sufficient emphasis on solutions, or a lack of representation of positive environmental initiatives. It is crucial for news outlets and journalists to consider the potential impact of consistently negative portrayals of environmental issues, as it can contribute to feelings of helplessness or resignation among the public. Efforts should be made to strike a balance between raising awareness about environmental challenges and highlighting positive developments, solutions, and opportunities for individual and collective action. The comparatively lower percentage of respondents with positive perceptions of environmental news suggests that there is room for improvement in portraying environmental issues in a positive light. Focusing on success stories, innovative solutions, and inspiring examples of environmental stewardship can help shift the narrative towards a more optimistic and empowering tone. Such positive framing can foster a sense of hope, motivation, and agency among the public, encouraging them to actively engage in environmental protection and sustainability efforts.

Figure 4.10 Environmental News Narratives

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusions

The relationship between climate change anxiety and behaviour is a multifaceted and intricate phenomenon. While some evidence suggests that climate anxiety can serve as a motivator for pro-environmental behaviour, the presence of eco-paralysis highlights potential barriers that individuals may encounter. To develop effective interventions and policies to address climate change challenges, further research is necessary to deepen our understanding of these dynamics. The higher prevalence of climate change anxiety among younger generations underscores the importance of acknowledging and addressing their concerns. It is crucial to comprehend the psychological impact of climate change anxiety on young individuals, as this knowledge can promote their well-being and facilitate their active participation in shaping sustainable solutions for the future. Furthermore, examining the impact of climate change on human health is essential for understanding the intricate relationship between climate change and anxiety. Pre-existing physical and mental health conditions can amplify individuals' vulnerability to climate change anxiety, underscoring the need for tailored support and interdisciplinary approaches. By acknowledging and addressing these connections and integrating health considerations into climate change strategies, we can foster well-being and resilience in the face of climate change challenges. Advancing our understanding of the complex relationship between climate change anxiety and behaviour, particularly among younger generations, and recognizing the interplay between climate change and human health will contribute to the development of comprehensive and effective approaches to address climate change and its psychological impacts.

Based on extensive literature reviews, it can be noted that Climate change anxiety in Myanmar is a significant issue with implications for the country's population and socio-economic well-being. The nation's vulnerability to climate change impacts exacerbates the challenges due to its unique geographical location and socio-economic factors. Limited infrastructure, inadequate resources, and lack of access to reliable information contribute to heightened anxiety. Climate change anxiety is manifested through fear of displacement, loss of livelihoods, and deteriorating living conditions. Targeted interventions and awareness campaigns are necessary to enhance environmental literacy and promote sustainable practices. Strengthening community resilience, providing mental health support, and seeking international collaboration can help address climate change anxiety in Myanmar, fostering a more secure and adaptive society for the future. Ultimately, this study has successfully accomplished its objectives, contributing to a deeper understanding of climate change anxiety

within the Myanmar framework. Firstly, through a comprehensive review of existing literature, the study has provided valuable insights into the relationship between climate change and anxiety, enhancing our understanding of the psychological dimensions associated with climate change impacts. Secondly, by selecting the most influential key factors on climate change anxiety in Myanmar, the study has identified the specific drivers and determinants of anxiety within the local context. This knowledge is crucial for developing targeted interventions and strategies to address climate change anxiety effectively. Thirdly, through an examination of the current situation of individuals residing in the study area by questionnaires, the study has provided empirical data on the prevalence and manifestations of climate change anxiety among the population in Myanmar. This assessment has offered valuable insights into the lived experiences and concerns of individuals, informing the development of context-specific interventions. Finally, by proposing effective and sustainable solutions to address the identified issue of climate change anxiety, the study has provided practical recommendations for mitigating anxiety and promoting resilience in the face of climate change. These solutions encompass a range of approaches, including awareness campaigns, community engagement, policy development, and support systems. To conclude, the completion of these objectives has significantly contributed to the understanding and management of climate change anxiety in Myanmar. The findings of this study offer valuable guidance for policymakers, practitioners, and researchers in addressing climate change anxiety and fostering sustainable responses to the climate challenges faced by individuals and communities in Myanmar

5.2 Recommendations

Based on a thorough review of the existing literature, several recommendations can be put forth to effectively address climate change anxiety in Myanmar. Firstly, there is a pressing need to enhance awareness and education regarding climate change and its consequences, with a particular focus on vulnerable communities. This can be achieved through targeted outreach programs, comprehensive public campaigns, and the integration of climate change education into formal education systems. Then, improving disaster preparedness is paramount in mitigating the impact of climate-related disasters, which significantly contribute to climate change anxiety. This entails investments in early warning systems, the enhancement of critical infrastructure, and the facilitation of access to emergency services. Moreover, recognizing the profound impact of climate change anxiety on mental health and well-being, it is imperative to ensure the availability and accessibility of mental health services. This necessitates the allocation of resources to bolster mental health infrastructure and the provision of training for

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healthcare providers in addressing climate change-related mental health challenges. Furthermore, promoting community engagement is vital to alleviate climate change anxiety and foster resilience in the face of climate-related disasters. Encouraging community-led disaster preparedness initiatives, supporting community-based adaptation programs, and empowering communities to undertake climate change mitigation efforts are crucial steps in this regard. Lastly, it is of utmost importance to emphasise the critical role of robust government action in effectively addressing the challenges posed by climate change. The government, in collaboration with not only NGOs and INGOs but also academic institutions must work in synergy to develop comprehensive solutions to combat climate change within the country. This entails joint efforts to devise preventive action plans specifically targeted at mitigating climate change anxiety and its adverse impacts. By fostering a strong partnership between the government, NGOs, and INGOs, the collective expertise, resources, and knowledge can be harnessed to create meaningful and sustainable interventions that address the complex issue of climate change anxiety in Myanmar. This encompasses the development and implementation of comprehensive climate change policies and programs, as well as substantial investments in climate-friendly infrastructure and technology. The implementation of these recommended actions is expected to alleviate climate change-related anxiety in Myanmar and enhance the populace's capacity to withstand the consequences of climate change. However, additional research is necessary to assess the effectiveness of these strategies and discover supplementary interventions that can be employed to effectively tackle this escalating issue.

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REFERENCES

- Abel, G. J., Brottrager, M., Cuaresma, J. C., & Muttarak, R. (2019). Climate, conflict and forced migration. *Global Environmental Change: Human and Policy Dimensions*, 54, 239–249. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2018.12.003>.
- Acharibasam, J. W., & Anuga, S. W. (2018). Psychological distance of climate change and mental health risks assessment of smallholder farmers in Northern Ghana: Is habituation a threat to climate change? *Climate Risk Management*, 21, 16–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crm.2018.04.002>.
- Aguilar, L., Araujo, A., & Quesada-Aguilar, A. (2008). Gender and Climate Change. International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN). Retrieved from <https://lib.icimod.org/record/13783/files/1337.pdf>.
- Alibudbud, R. C. (2022). Climate change and mental health in the Philippines. *BJPsych International*. Retrieved from <https://www.cambridge.org/core/services/aop-cambridge-core/content/view/2C38EEC4ACC529448C359951B028B1CE/S2056474022000319a.pdf>.
- American Psychological Association. (2021, March 1). Addressing climate change concerns in practice. American Psychological Association. Retrieved March 25, 2023, from <https://www.apa.org/monitor/2021/03/ce-climate-change>.
- Anderson, C. (2001). Heat and Violence. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8721.00109>.
- Aruta, J. J. B., & Guinto, R. (2022). Climate anxiety in the Philippines: Current situation, potential pathways, and ways forward. *The Journal of Climate Change and Health*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcchn.2022.100079>.
- Ballew, M., Maibach, E., Kotcher, J., Bergquist, P., Rosenthal, S., Marlon, J., & Leiserowitz, A. (2020, April 16). Which racial/ethnic groups care most about climate change? Yale Program on Climate Change Communication. Retrieved April 27, 2023, from <https://climatecommunication.yale.edu/publications/race-and-climate-change/>.
- Blanc, J., Spruill, T. M., Butler, M. S., Casimir, G., & Jean-Louis, G. (2019). 0885 Is Resilience A Protective Factor For Sleep Disturbances Among Earthquake Survivors? *Sleep*, 42(Supplement_1), A356. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sleep/zsz067.883>.

- Bloemendaal, N., & Moel, H. d. (2022). A globally consistent local-scale assessment of future tropical cyclone risk. *Science Advances*, 8, eabm8438. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abm8438>.
- Bourque, F. Ç. O., & Cunsolo, A. (2014). Climate change: The next challenge for public mental health? *International Review of Psychiatry*, 26(4), 415–422. <https://doi.org/10.3109/09540261.2014.925851>.
- Chen, J. (2005). China's Way of Economic Transition. *Far East and Asian Studies*, 4(3), 40-48. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11300-005-0064-x>.
- China Center for Climate Change Communication. (2017). Climate Change in the Chinese Mind Survey Report 2017. China Center for Climate Change Communication. Retrieved from <https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/Press%20Release%20-%20202.pdf>.
- Cianconi, P., Betrò, S., & Janiri, L. (2020). The Impact of Climate Change on Mental Health: A Systematic Descriptive Review. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 11, 74. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2020.00074>.
- Clayton, S. (2020). Climate anxiety: Psychological responses to climate change. *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, 74, 102283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.janxdis.2020.102283>.
- Clayton, S., Manning, C., Krygsman, K., & Speiser, M. (2017). Mental health and our changing climate: Impacts, implications, and guidance. Washington, DC: American Psychological Association and ecoAmerica. Retrieved from <https://www.apa.org/news/press/releases/2017/03/mental-health-climate.pdf>.
- Climate Psychology Alliance. (2020). The Handbook of Climate Psychology. Retrieved from <https://www.climatepsychologyalliance.org/images/files/handbookofclimatepsychology.pdf>.
- Closson, K., Card, K., Logi, C., Aran, N., Sachal, A. S., Bratu, A., Marshall, C., Hu, A., Takaro, T., Kennedy, A., Clayton, S., Samji, H., & Martin, G. (2021). Gender Differences in Climate Change Anxiety. SSRN. Retrieved from https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4168583.
- Coffey, Y., Bhullar, N., Durkin, J., Islam, M. S., & Usher, K. (2021). Understanding Eco-anxiety: A Systematic Scoping Review of Current Literature and Identified Knowledge Gaps. *The Journal of Climate Change and Health*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocch.2021.100280>.
- Collier, S. (2022, June 13). If climate change keeps you up at night, here's how to cope. Harvard Health. Retrieved March 26, 2023, from <https://www.health.harvard.edu/blog/is->

climate-change-keeping-you-up-at-night-you-may-have-climate-anxiety-202206132761.

- Comtesse, H., Ertl, V., Hengst, S., Rosner, R., & Smid, G. (2021). Ecological Grief as a Response to Environmental Change: A Mental Health Risk or Functional Response? *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(2), 734. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18020734>.
- Dechezleprêtre, A., Fabre, A., Kruse, T., Planterose, B., Chico, A., & Stantcheva, S. (2022). Fighting climate change: International attitudes toward climate policies. OECD Economics Department Working Papers, No. 1645. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1787/3406f29a-en>.
- Eckstein, D., Künzel, V., & Schäfer, L. (2021). Global Climate Risk Index 2021. Germanwatch. Retrieved from <https://www.germanwatch.org/en/19777>.
- Fountoulakis, K., Chatzikosta, I., Pasiadis, K., Zanis, P., & Kawohl, W. (2016). Relationship of suicide rates with climate and economic variables in Europe during 2000–2012. *Annals of General Psychiatry*, 15, 23. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12991-016-0105-8>
- Frontier Myanmar. (2022). Suicides surge in post-coup Myanmar. Frontier Myanmar. Retrieved from <https://www.frontiermyanmar.net/en/suicides-surge-in-post-coup-myanmar/>.
- Ghimire, U., Piman, T., Shrestha, M., Aryal, A., & Krittasudthacheewa, C. (2022). Assessment of Climate Change Impacts on the Water, Food, and Energy Sectors in Sittaung River Basin, Myanmar. *Water*, 14(21), 3434. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w14213434>.
- Goleman, D. (2019). The Age of Eco-Angst. *The New York Times*. Retrieved from <https://archive.nytimes.com/opinionator.blogs.nytimes.com/2009/09/27/the-age-of-eco-angst/>.
- Hart, P. S., & Feldman, L. (2016). The Influence of Climate Change Efficacy Messages and Efficacy Beliefs on Intended Political Participation. *PLOS ONE*, 11(8), e0157658. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0157658>.
- Hibberd, M., & Nguyen, A. (2013). Climate change communications & young people in the United Kingdom: A reception study. *International Journal of Media and Cultural Politics*, 9(3), 299-315. https://doi.org/10.1386/macp.9.3.299_1.
- Hickerman, C., Marks, E., Pihkala, P., Clayton, S., & Lewandowski, E. (2021). Climate anxiety in children and young people and their beliefs about government responses to climate change: a global survey. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 5(12), e863-e873. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(21\)00278-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(21)00278-3).

- India Meteorological Department. (2021). India Meteorological Department Annual Report 2021. Ministry of Earth Sciences, India. Retrieved from https://mausam.imd.gov.in/imd_latest/contents/ar2021.pdf.
- IPCC. (2022). IPCC Sixth Assessment Report. Retrieved from <https://www.ipcc.ch/assessment-report/ar6/>.
- Kim, E. J. (2016). The impacts of climate change on human health in the United States: A scientific assessment, by US global change research program. *Journal of the American Planning Association*, 82(4), 418-419.
- Larionow, P., Sołtys, M., Izdebski, P., Mudło-Głagolska, K., Golonka, J., Demski, M., & Rosińska, M. (2022). Climate Change Anxiety Assessment: The Psychometric Properties of the Polish Version of the Climate Anxiety Scale. *National Library of Medicine*. Retrieved from <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35645848/>.
- Larsen, K., Pitt, H., Grant, M., & Houser, T. (2021, May 6). China's Greenhouse Gas Emissions Exceeded the Developed World for the First Time in 2019. Rhodium Group. Retrieved April 21, 2023, from <https://rhg.com/research/chinas-emissions-surpass-developed-countries/>.
- Lee, T. M., Markowitz, E., Howe, P., Ko, C.-Y., & Leiserowitz, A. (2015). Predictors of public climate change awareness and risk perception around the world. *Nature Climate Change*. Retrieved from https://na.eventscloud.com/file_uploads/7ce0ee53ff0a88e07c6c2224afd8efa6_InspirationPredictorsofpublicclimatechangeawarenessandriskperceptionaroundtheworld1.pdf.
- Lee Health. (2022). After the Storm: How to Deal with Mental Health Challenges. Lee Health. Retrieved May 5, 2023, from <https://www.leehealth.org/health-and-wellness/healthy-news-blog/health-hub/after-the-storm-how-to-deal-with-mental-health-challenges>.
- Lindsay, S., Hsu, S., Rangunathan, S., & Lindsay, J. (2022). The impact of climate change related extreme weather events on people with pre-existing disabilities and chronic conditions: a scoping review. *PubMed*. Retrieved from <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36426560/>.
- Mallett, R. K. (2012). Eco-Guilt motivates Eco-Friendly Behaviour (Vol. 4). Mary Ann Liebert Incorporated. <https://doi.org/10.1089/eco.2012.0031>.
- Maran, D. A., & Begotti, T. (2021). Media Exposure to Climate Change, Anxiety, and Efficacy Beliefs in a Sample of Italian University Students. *International Journal of*

- Environmental Research and Public Health. Retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8431103/>
- Mayo Clinic. (2021). Anxiety disorders - Symptoms and causes. Mayo Clinic. Retrieved May 10, 2023, from <https://www.mayoclinic.org/diseases-conditions/anxiety/symptoms-causes/syc-20350961>.
- Myanmar Information Management Unit. (2022). Climate, Environmental Degradation and Disaster Risk in Myanmar. Myanmar Information Management Unit. Retrieved from https://themimu.info/sites/themimu.info/files/documents/Report_Analytical_Brief_Climate_Environmental_Degradation_and_Disaster_Risk_MIMU_May2022_ENG.pdf.
- Marks, E., Hickman, C., Pihkala, P., Clayton, S., Lewandowski, E. R., Mayall, E. E., Wray, B., Mellor, C., & van Susteren, L. (2021). Young People's Voices on Climate Anxiety, Government Betrayal and Moral Injury: A Global Phenomenon. Retrieved from SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3918955> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3918955>.
- NASA. (2023, January 12). NASA Says 2022 Fifth Warmest Year on Record, Warming Trend Continues – Climate Change: Vital Signs of the Planet. NASA Climate Change. Retrieved March 27, 2023, from <https://climate.nasa.gov/news/3246/nasa-says-2022-fifth-warmest-year-on-record-warming-trend-continues/>.
- National Climate Change Secretariat. (2020). Impact Of Climate Change In Singapore - Singapore's Climate Targets. National Climate Change Secretariat. Retrieved April 22, 2023, from <https://www.nccs.gov.sg/singapores-climate-action/impact-of-climate-change-in-singapore/>.
- National Geographic Society. (2022, July 15). Deforestation. National Geographic Society. Retrieved May 9, 2023, from <https://education.nationalgeographic.org/resource/deforestation/>.
- National Institute of Mental Health and Neuro Science, India. (2016). CLIMATE CHANGE and MENTAL HEALTH. National Centre for Disease Control. Retrieved March 26, 2023, from <https://ncdc.mohfw.gov.in/WriteReadData/linkimages/Zoonoticdiseasesclimatechange.pdf>.
- National Institute of Mental Health and Neuro Sciences, India. (2016). Climate change and mental health. National Institute of Mental Health and Neuro Sciences, India.

- Ogunbode, C., Doran, R., Hanss, D., Ojala, M., Salmela-Aro, K., & van den Broek, K. (2022). Climate anxiety, wellbeing and pro-environmental action: correlates of negative emotional responses to climate change in 32 countries. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 84. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0272494422001323>.
- Paolo, C., Sophia, B., & Luigi, J. (2020). The Impact of Climate Change on Mental Health: A Systematic Descriptive Review. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 11. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyt.2020.00074>.
- Pihkala, P. (2019). Climate Anxiety. MIELI Mental Health Finland. <http://hdl.handle.net/10138/307626>.
- Sandy, M. (2022). Why Is the Amazon RainForest Disappearing? | Time. TIME. Retrieved from <https://time.com/amazon-rainforest-disappearing/>.
- Schwirplies, C. (2017). Citizens' Acceptance of Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation: A Survey in China, Germany, and the U.S. *Ecological Economics*, 137, 131-141. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0921800917300599>.
- Schwartz, S.E.O., Benoit, L., Clayton, S., et al. (2022). Climate change anxiety and mental health: Environmental activism as a buffer. *Current Psychology*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-022-02735-6>.
- The World Bank Group. (2022). China Country Climate and Development Report. Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/china/publication/china-country-climate-and-development-report>.
- Thompson, T. (2021). Young people's climate anxiety revealed in landmark survey. *Nature*, 597, 605. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-021-02582-8>.
- United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs. (2008, June 12). Myanmar: Coping with cyclone trauma - Myanmar. ReliefWeb. Retrieved from <https://reliefweb.int/report/myanmar/myanmar-coping-cyclone-trauma>.
- Usher, K., Durkin, J., & Bhullar, N. (2019). Eco-anxiety: How thinking about climate change-related environmental decline is affecting our mental health. *International Journal of Mental Health Nursing*, 28(6), 1233-1234. <https://doi.org/10.1111/inm.12673>.
- Ursano, R. J., Morganstein, J. C., & Cooper, R. (2017). APA resource document: Mental health and climate change. Retrieved from [Mental-Health-Climate-Change.pdf](#).
- UN-Habitat. (2019). Assessing Climate Risk in Myanmar: Technical Report. Retrieved from https://unhabitat.org/sites/default/files/2019/10/assessing-climate-risk-in-myanmar_technical-report.pdf.

- US International Trade Administration. (2022, July 28). Burma - Healthcare. US International Trade Administration. Retrieved May 27, 2023, from <https://www.trade.gov/country-commercial-guides/burma-healthcare>.
- Volcano Discovery. (2023). Past Earthquakes in Yangon, Myanmar. Volcano Discovery. Retrieved May 27, 2023, from <https://www.volcanodiscovery.com/place/16289/earthquakes/yangon/archive/2022-01-01-2023-01-01.html>.
- Wang, B., & Zhou, Q. (2020). Climate change in the Chinese mind: An overview of public perceptions at macro and micro levels. *WIREs Climate Change*, 11(3), e639. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.639>.
- Whitmarsh, L., Player, L., Jiongco, A., James, M., Williams, M., Marks, E., & Kennedy-Williams, P. (2022). Climate anxiety: What predicts it and how is it related to climate action? *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 83, 101542. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0272494422001116#abs0015>
- World Bank Group. (2022). Philippines Country Climate and Development Report. World Bank, Washington DC. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/10986/38280>.
- World Health Organization & World Health Organization. (2014). Gender, Climate Change and Health. World Health Organization (WHO). Retrieved from https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/144781/9789241508186_eng.pdf
- World Health Organization. Department of Gender, Women and Health & World Health Organization. Department of Public Health and Environment. (2014). Gender, Climate Change and Health. World Health Organization (WHO). Retrieved from http://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/144781/9789241508186_eng.pdf;jsessionid=E77F1C480C129BCD940C83BDF9152F05?sequence=1.
- Wullenkord, M., Tröger, J., Hamann, K., Loy, L., & Reese, G. (2021). Anxiety and climate change: a validation of the Climate Anxiety Scale in a German-speaking quota sample and an investigation of psychological correlates. *Climatic Change*, 168, 1787-1805. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10584-021-03234-6#citeas>.
- World Bank. (2020). Myanmar - Vulnerability | Climate Change Knowledge Portal. Climate Change Knowledge Portal. Retrieved May 29, 2023, from <https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/country/myanmar/vulnerability>.
- World Health Organization. (2018). WHO COUNTRY COOPERATION STRATEGIC AGENDA (2014–2018). WHO.

http://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/136952/ccsbrief_mmr_en.pdf;jsessionid=B867D92DFC3CE007D6BAE753CCA23946?sequence=1.

- Yale Project on Climate Change Communication. (2012). Climate Change in the Indian Mind. Yale University. Retrieved from https://climatecommunication.yale.edu/wp-content/uploads/2016/02/2012_08_Climate-Change-in-the-Indian-Mind.pdf.
- Yu, H., Wang, B., Zhang, Y.-J., Wang, S., & Wei, Y.-M. (2013). Public Perception of Climate Change in China: Results from the Questionnaire Survey. ResearchGate. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/257633523_Public_Perception_of_Climate_Change_in_China_Results_from_the_Questionnaire_Survey.

APEENDIX: Questionnaire

လူထုစစ်တမ်းကောက်ယူမှုမေးခွန်းလွှာ

The Environmental Health and Safety Myanmar (EHS Myanmar) အဖွဲ့သည် Research Team ၏ ဦးဆောင်မှုဖြင့် “A Review and Assessment on Climate Change in Yangon” ဆိုသည့် ခေါင်းစဉ်ဖြင့် သုတေသနစာတမ်း တစ်ခု ပြုလုပ်လျက်ရှိရာ ထိုစာတမ်းအတွက် စစ်တမ်း ကောက်ယူခြင်း ဖြစ်ပါသည်။ စစ်တမ်းတွက် မေးခွန်း ၃၅ ခုပါဝင်ပြီး အချိန်အားဖြင့် (၃) မိနစ်မှ (၅) မိနစ်သာ ကြာမြင့်မည် ဖြစ်ပါသည်။ ယခုလို စစ်တမ်းတွင် ပါဝင်ပေးသည့်အတွက် လူကြီးမင်းတို့အားကျေးဇူးတင်ပါသည်။

First of all, we need your consent to participate in this survey. I, hereby, agree to participate in it by providing genuine responses to every asked question. (စစ်တမ်းကောက်ယူမှုတွင် ပါဝင်ရန်အတွက် လူကြီးမင်း၏ သဘောတူညီမှုကိုရယူလိုပါသည်။)

Part 1. Demographic Factors

၁။ သင်နေထိုင်ရာမြို့နယ်ကိုပြောပြပေးပါ။

၂။ ကျား/ မ

a) မ b) ကျား c) မဖော်ပြလိုပါ

၃။ သင့်အသက်

a) အသက် ၁၈ နှစ်အောက် b) အသက် ၁၈ နှင့် ၂၅ ကြား c) အသက် ၂၆ နှင့် ၃၀ ကြား d) အသက် ၃၁ နှင့် ၃၅ ကြား e) အသက် ၃၆ နှင့် ၄၀ ကြား f) အသက် ၄၀ နှင့် ၄၅ ကြား g) အသက် ၄၀ နှင့် အထက်

၄။ သင့်ပညာအရည်အချင်း

a) ၁၀ တန်း အောင်မြင်ပြီးသူ b) ဘွဲ့ကြို c) ဒီပလိုမာ d) ဘွဲ့ရရှိပြီးသူ e) မဟာဘွဲ့
f) ဒေါက်တာဘွဲ့ g) အခြား h) မဖော်ပြလိုပါ

Part 2. Socioeconomic Factors

၁။ သင့်ရဲ့ လက်ရှိ အလုပ်အကိုင်ကို ဖော်ပြပေးပါ။

- a) အချိန်ပြည့်ဝန်ထမ်း
- b) အချိန်ပိုင်းဝန်ထမ်း
- c) အလုပ်ရှာနေဆဲ
- d) ပင်စင်ယူထားပြီး
- e) လတ်တလော အလုပ်မရှိ/မလုပ်သေးပါ

၂။ တစ်လအတွင်းရရှိသောသင့်ဝင်ငွေကိုပြောပြပေးပါ။

- a) ကျပ်၃သိန်းအောက်
- b) ကျပ်၃သိန်းနှင့်၆သိန်း ကြား
- c) ဝင်ငွေ ၆သိန်းနှင့်၁၀သိန်းကြား
- d) ဝင်ငွေ ၁၀ သိန်း အထက်
- e) မဖော်ပြလိုပါ

၃။ သင့်မှာမိသားစုဝင်ဘယ်နှစ်ယောက်ရှိပါသလဲ။

- a) မိသားစုဝင် ၁ဦး မှ ၂ ဦး
- b) မိသားစုဝင် ၂ဦး မှ ၃ ဦး
- c) မိသားစုဝင် ၃ဦး မှ ၄ဦး
- d) ၄ဦး နှင့် အထက်

၄။ သင့်ဝင်ငွေဖြင့်လုံလောက်မှု ရှိ/မရှိ။

- a) ရှိပါသည်)
- b) မရှိပါ

Part 3. Environmental Factors

၁။ သင် သဘာဝဘေးအန္တရာယ်တစ်ခုခုနှင့်ကို ရင်ဆိုင်တွေ့ကြုံဖူးပါသလား။

- a) တိုက်ရိုက်ကြုံဖူးပါသည်
- b) သွယ်ဝိုက်၍ကြုံဖူးပါသည်
- c) လုံးဝမကြုံဖူးပါ

၂။ ဘယ်လိုသဘာဝဘေးအန္တရာယ်နဲ့ ရင်ဆိုင်ခဲ့ဖူးပါသလဲ။

- a) အပူလှိုင်းဖြတ်ခြင်း
- b) အအေးလွန်ကဲခြင်း
- c) မိုးခေါင်ခြင်း
- e) ရေကြီးခြင်း
- f) တောမီးလောင်ခြင်း
- g) ငလျင်လှုပ်ခြင်း
- h) ဆိုင်ကလုန်းမုန်တိုင်းတိုက်ခတ်ခြင်း
- i) အခြား

၃။ ဒီသဘာဝဘေးအန္တရာယ်ကြောင့် သင်ဘယ်လောက်ထိစိတ်ဒဏ်ရာရခဲ့ပါသလဲ။

- a) အနည်းငယ်မျှ b) အနည်းငယ်ထက်ပို) c) အတန်အသင့်)
- d) အနည်းငယ်ပြင်းထန် (e) ပြင်းပြင်းထန်ထန်

၄။ ဒီသဘာဝ ဘေးအန္တရာယ်တွေကြောင့် စီးပွားရေးမှာ သင်ဘယ်လောက်ထိနစ်နာ ဆုံးရှုံးခဲ့ရပါသလဲ။

- a) အနည်းငယ်မျှ b) အနည်းငယ်ထက်ပို c) အတန်အသင့်
- d) အနည်းငယ်ပြင်းထန် e) ပြင်းပြင်းထန်ထန်

၅။ အကယ်၍ ဒီလိုသဘာဝဘေးအန္တရာယ်တွေ ရှေ့လျှောက် ရှိလာဦးမယ်ဆိုရင် သင်ဘယ်လောက် စိတ်ထိခိုက်ရမယ်လို့ ထင်ပါသလဲ။

- a) အနည်းငယ်မျှ b) အနည်းငယ်ထက်ပို c) အတန်အသင့်
- d) အနည်းငယ်ပြင်းထန် e) ပြင်းပြင်းထန်ထန်

၆။ သင့်တွင်နဂိုရှိပြီးသား ကျန်းမာရေးအားနည်းချက်များရှိပါသလား။

- a) မရှိပါ b) သိုင်းရွိုက်ရောဂါ c) သွေးတိုး
- e) ကင်ဆာ f) ဆီးချို g) အခြား

၇။ Climate-change Anxiety ဆိုတာ ဘာလဲဆိုတာ သင်ဘယ်လောက်ထိ သိပါသလဲ။

- a) မကြားဖူးပါ b) အနည်းငယ်ရင်းနှီး c) အတန်အတင့်ရင်းနှီး
- d) အလွန်ရင်းနှီး e) ကောင်းကောင်းနားလည်သည်။

၈။ ပူပင်သောက ရှိခြင်းက ကောင်းတယ်လို့ ထင်ပါသလား၊ ဆိုးတယ်လို့ ထင်ပါသလား။

- a) အဆိုးဆုံး b) ဆိုး c) သာမန် d) အနည်းငယ်သဘောတူ
- f) လုံးဝသဘောတူ

၉။ ဘာလို့ ပူပင် သောကရှိခြင်းက ကောင်းတယ် (သို့မဟုတ်) မကောင်းဘူးလို့ ထင်ပါသလဲ။

၁၀။ ယခုနှစ်တွေအတွင်းမှာ စီးပွားရေး၊ လူမှုရေး၊ နိုင်ငံရေး၊ ပညာရေး တို့နှင့် ပတ်သတ်ပြီး စိုးရိမ်ပူပန်မှုတို့ကို ခံစားခဲ့ရသည်။

- a) လုံးဝသဘောမတူ b) အနည်းငယ်သဘောမတူ c) ကြားနေ
- d) အနည်းငယ်သဘောတူ e) လုံးဝသဘောတူ

၁၁။ ဒီလိုခံစားရဖူးတယ်ဆိုရင် တစ်ပတ်မှာ သင် ဘယ်နှစ်ရက် လောက် ခံစားရပါသလဲ

- a) မခံစားဘူးပါ
- b) တစ်ရက်
- c) နှစ်ရက်
- d) သုံးရက်
- e) လေးရက်
- f) ငါးရက်
- h) ခြောက်ရက်
- i) ခုနစ်ရက်

၁၂။ ကာဗွန်ဒိုင်အောက်ဆိုဒ်၊ မီသိန်း နှင့် အိုဇုန်ဓာတ်ငွေ့များသည် ကမ္ဘာ့လေထုထဲတွင် အပူများကိုဖမ်းယူနိုင်သော ဖန်လုံအိမ်ဓာတ်ငွေ့များဖြစ်သည်။

- a) မှား
- b) မှန်
- c) အဖြေမပါရှိပါ

၁၃။ ကမ္ဘာကြီးပူနွေးလာခြင်းသည် လူသားများအပေါ်တွင်သာ သက်ရောက်မှုများစွာရှိပြီး တိရိစ္ဆာန်များအပေါ်တွင် သက်ရောက်မှုမရှိပါ။

- a) မှား
- b) မှန်
- c) အဖြေမပါရှိပါ

၁၄။ လေထုညစ်ညမ်းမှု ဖြစ်နေပါက ထိုသို့ဖြစ်နေခြင်းကို သင်မြင်နိုင်၍ အနံ့လည်းရနိုင်ပါသည်။

- a) မှား
- b) မှန်
- c) အဖြေမပါရှိပါ

၁၅။ ကလိုရိုဖလူရိုကာဗွန်များသည် လေထုအတွင်းရှိ အိုဇုန်းလွှာကို လျော့နည်း လာစေသည်။

- a) မှား
- b) မှန်
- c) အဖြေမပါရှိပါ

၁၆။ သင်သဘာဝပတ်ဝန်းကျင်မှာ အလုပ်လုပ်ခြင်းဖြင့် အချိန်ဘယ်လောက်ကုန်ဆုံးဖြစ်လဲ။

- a) နေ့စဉ်
- b) အပတ်စဉ်
- c) နှစ်ပတ်တစ်ကြိမ်
- d) သုံးပတ်တစ်ကြိမ်
- e) တစ်လတစ်ကြိမ်

၁၇။ သဘာဝပတ်ဝန်းကျင် ထိန်းသိမ်းခြင်းအတွက် အလုပ်လုပ်ခြင်းဖြင့် သင့်မိသားအနေဖြင့် အချိန်ဘယ်လောက် ကုန်ဆုံးဖြစ်လဲ။

- a) နေ့စဉ်
- b) အပတ်စဉ်
- c) နှစ်ပတ်တစ်ကြိမ်
- d) သုံးပတ်တစ်ကြိမ်
- e) တစ်လတစ်ကြိမ်

၁၈။ ရာသီဥတုပြောင်းလဲခြင်းကို တိုက်ဖျက်ရန်အတွက် သင်အချိန်ဘယ်လောက်ပေးဖြစ်ပါလဲ။

- a) နေ့စဉ်
- b) အပတ်စဉ်
- c) နှစ်ပတ်တစ်ကြိမ်
- d) သုံးပတ်တစ်ကြိမ်
- e) တစ်လတစ်ကြိမ်

၁၉။ သင့်ရဲ့ ကိုယ်ပိုင်ဝင်ငွေထဲက ရာသီဥတုပြောင်းလဲမှုကို ကာကွယ်ရန်အတွက် ဘယ်လောက်ပမာဏအထိသုံးဖြစ်ပါသလဲ။

- a) လုံးဝမသုံးဖြစ်ပါ
- b) ၂၅%
- c) ၅၀%
- d) ၇၅%
- e) ရာနှုန်းပြည့်

၂၀။ ကာဗွန်အသုံးပြုမှုနည်းသည့် လူနေမှုပုံစံကို လူတွေလုံးဝနေထိုင်နိုင်မည်။ သင်သဘောတူပါသလား။

- a) သဘောမတူ
- b) အနည်းငယ်သဘောမတူပါ
- c) သာမန်
- d) အနည်းငယ်သဘောတူပါသည်
- e) လုံးဝသဘောတူ

၂၁။ ကာဗွန်နည်းသော သယ်ယူပို့ဆောင်ရေးစနစ်ကိုလူတွေလုံးဝနေထိုင်နိုင်မည်။ သင်သဘောတူပါသလား။

- a) သဘောမတူ
- b) အနည်းငယ်သဘောမတူပါ
- c) Neutral (သာမန်)
- d) အနည်းငယ်သဘောတူပါသည်
- e) လုံးဝသဘောတူ

၂၂။ သင်သဘာဝပတ်ဝန်းကျင်ထိန်းသိမ်းရေးနဲ့ ပတ်သက်တဲ့ သတင်းများ၊ ဆောင်းပါးများ ဖတ်ဖူး၊ နားထောင်ဖူး၊ ကြည့်ဖူးပါသလား။

- a) လုပ်ဖူးပါသည်
- b) မလုပ်ဖူးပါ
- c) မသေချာပါ

၂၃။ ထိုသဘာဝပတ်ဝန်းကျင်ဆိုင်ရာ သတင်းများကို ဘယ်လောက်ထိ ဖတ်ဖြစ်ပါသလဲ။)

- a) နေ့စဉ်
- b) အပတ်စဉ်
- c) နှစ်ပတ်တစ်ကြိမ်
- d) သုံးပတ်တစ်ကြိမ်
- e) တစ်လတစ်ကြိမ်

၂၄။ ထိုသဘာဝပတ်ဝန်းကျင်ဆိုင်ရာ သတင်းအများစုသည် အကောင်းဘက်မြင်တဲ့သတင်းများ လား၊ ဆိုးတဲ့ဘက်ကမြင်တဲ့သတင်းများလား။

- a) သတင်းဆိုးများ
- b) သတင်းဆိုးအနည်းငယ်များ
- c) သာမန်
- d) သတင်းကောင်းအနည်းငယ်များ
- e) သတင်းကောင်းများ

APPENDIX: Photos

Photo A1: EHS Myanmar Team Members

Photo A2: Interview Meeting with Ms. Khin Moe Myint

Photo A3: Data Enumerators Training Sessions